

Classical *Tafsīr al-Mathūr* and *Tafsīr al-Rā'y* on Qur'ān 4:34

Translations of al-Māwardī (1058CE/450AH) and al-Māturīdī
(944CE/333AH)'s exegesis, with an analysis of differences in sources,
methodology and human ontology

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In this analysis we have provided the translation of two classical exegetes on Qur'ān verse 4:34, the infamous 'beating verse'¹, whereby we will analyze the differences and similarities in the exegesis of the theologian al-Māturīdī and of the jurist al-Māwardī. We will analyse the differences in used sources and applied methodology, but also in the presented human ontology. In this way we can analyze how the different methodologies construct and even eliminate the possible meanings of the Qur'ānic text.

The exegetes and their methodical approach

The Shafī'ī scholar Abī al-Ḥassan al-Māwardī (d. 1058CE/450AH) from Basra, is famous for his work on Shari'a governance, *Aḥkām al-Sultāniyya wa al-Wāliyyat al-Dīniyya*.² Al-Māwardī's exegetical style belongs to the *tafsīr bi-lMathūr*, exegesis through tradition, and more specifically to the *tafsīr al-Qur'ān bi-aqwal al-Ṣaḥāba wa al-Tābi'ūn*, exegesis of the Qur'ān through the sayings of the companions and their followers, and rarely provide his own personal interpretations.³ Al-Māwardī combines linguistic exegesis (*gharīb al-Qur'ān* or *tafsīr bil-Lughā*)⁴, with exegesis through prophetic traditions (*Aḥādīth*) and general traditions (*Athār*) containing sayings from the prophetic companions and their followers. His *tafsīr* leans heavily on the famous *tafsīr* of Ibn Jarīr al-Ṭabarī (d. 933CE/310AH), the main source of the *tafsīr bi-lMathūr* genre⁵, as will be shown below. The Ḥanafī scholar Abī Maṣṣūr al-Māturīdī (d. 944CE/333AH) from Samarqand, is famous for his theological work, *Kitāb al-Tawḥīd*, and is the founder of one of the Sunni orthodox schools

¹ For an extensive discussion on classical and modern exegetical traditions, and the modern discomfort, surrounding this verse, see: Ayesha Chaudhry, *Domestic Violence and the Islamic Tradition* (London: Oxford University Press, 2016). Jonathan A. C. Brown, *Misquoting Muhammad: The challenge and choices of interpreting the prophet's legacy* (United Kingdom: Oneworld Publications, 2014), 268–90.

² On al-Māwardī, see: *Encyclopaedia of Islam, Second Edition* (2012), s.v "Al-Māwardī" by C. Brockelmann, edited by P. Bearman e.a., accessed August 15, 2016, http://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/encyclopaedia-of-islam-2/al-mawardi-COM_0713.

³ For a discussion on this specific form of *tafsīr*, see: Hussein Abdul-Raof, *Schools of Qur'anic Exegesis: Genesis and development* (Abingdon: Routledge, 2010), 5-9, 157-161.

⁴ On linguistic *tafsīr*, see: Abdul-Raof, *Schools of Qur'anic Exegesis*, 30-32, 169-208. Hussein Abdul-Raof, *Theological approaches to Qur'anic exegesis: A practical comparative-contrastive analysis* (London: Taylor & Francis, 2010), 83–142.

⁵ On *tafsīr bi-lMathūr*, see: Abdul-Raof, *Schools of Qur'anic Exegesis*, 112-168. Abdul-Raof, *Theological approaches to Qur'anic exegesis*, 10-27. Aḥmad b. 'Abd Allah al-Baghdādī, "al-Tafsīr bi-lMā'thūr Jama' wa Darāsāt Naqdiyyat min Sūrat al-Nisā'", (Cairo, 1999), 10–20, Jāma'at al-Azhar Kulliyat Uṣūl al-Dīn. On al-Ṭabarī as the epitome of this genre, see: Ignaz Goldziher, *Schools of Koranic Commentators: With an Introduction on Goldziher and Hadith from "Geschichte Des Arabischen Schrifttums" by Fuat Sezgin*, edited by Wolfgang Behn (Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz in Kommission, 2006), 56–69. Herbert Berg, *The development of exegesis in early Islam: The authenticity of Muslim literature from the formative period* (London, United Kingdom: Taylor & Francis, 2009), 120–141.

of theology.⁶ According to al-Māturīdī, there are two methods of exegesis, (1) *tafsīr*, which according to him is based on the prophetic Sunna and the opinions of the prophetic companions who know the reason of revelation (*sabab al-nuzūl*)⁷ from which the revealed command (*amr*) and intent (*murād*) can be derived; and (2) *ta'wīl*, the rational interpretations by the jurist-theologians, the *fuqahā'*, who through the use of reasoned opinion (*rā'y*) extend the meaning and implications of this command and intent to its utmost limit.⁸ Therefore al-Māturīdī's classification of *tafsīr* is similar to the classification of *tafsīr bi-lMathūr*, and *ta'wīl* to *tafsīr bi-lRā'y*.⁹ In his exegesis of 4:34, both methods are present, but mostly contains *tafsīr bi-lRā'y* due to his discussions on the possible juristic (*Fiqh*) meanings and implications of this verse.¹⁰ The importance of al-Māturīdī's *tafsīr* for the understanding of the development of Sunni exegesis is that it shows that *tafsīr bi-lRā'y*, especially its *Kalamic* form, isn't simply a heterodox or late development, but has since the beginning been intrinsic to Sunni engagements of the Qur'ān.¹¹

Qur'ān verse 4:34 and its key terms

الرِّجَالُ قَوَّامُونَ عَلَى النِّسَاءِ بِمَا فَضَّلَ اللَّهُ بَعْضَهُمْ عَلَى بَعْضٍ وَبِمَا أَنْفَقُوا مِنْ أَمْوَالِهِمْ فَالصَّالِحَاتُ قَنَاطٌ لَّغَيْبٍ بِمَا حَفِظَ اللَّهُ ۗ وَاللَّيِّئَاتُ تُخَافُونَ أَنْسُوهُنَّ فِعْظُهُنَّ وَآهَجُرُوهُنَّ فِي الْمَضَاجِعِ وَأَضْرِبُوهُنَّ فَإِنْ أَطَعْنَكُمْ فَلَا تَبْغُوا عَلَيْهِنَّ سَبِيلًا إِنَّ اللَّهَ كَانَ عَلِيمًا كَبِيرًا

Qur'ān 4:34. {Men are the maintainers (*qawwāmūn*) of women, because God has made one of them excel (*faḍḍala*) the other, and because they spend (*anfaqū*) of their wealth (*amwālihum*). So virtuous women (*al-ṣāliḥāt*) are those who are obedient (*qānitāt*) and guardians of the absence (*ḥāfiẓāt li-lGhayb*), in what God has guarded. As from those women you fear ill-conduct (*nushūzahun*), you may admonish them (*fa-izūhunna*) and [then] abandon them (*ahjurūhunna*) in their beds with them and [then] beat them (*aḍribūhunna*). If they, then, obey you (*aṭa'nakum*), you shall seek no other way (*sabīlān*) against them. Indeed, God alone is High, [and] Great.}

⁶ On al-Māturīdī, see: Mustafa Ceric, *Roots of Synthetic Theology in Islām: A study of the theology of Abu Mansur Al-Maturidi (d. 333/944)* (Kuala Lumpur: ISTAC, 1995); Ulrich Rudolph, *Al-Māturīdī and the Development of Sunnī Theology in Samarqand* (Leiden: Brill, 2015), 125ff.

⁷ *Sabab al-nuzūl* (pl. *Asbāb al-nuzūl*) literally means cause or reason of the sending down, and refers to a historical situation surrounding the prophet Muhammad which triggered or demanded the sending down of revelation. The *asbāb* traditions therefore belong to the *Hadīth* genre, but are generally considered weak in transmission (*isnad*). Abdul-Raof, *Schools of Qur'anic Exegesis*, 40. Muḥammad b. Muḥammad Abū Shahba, *al-Madkhal li-Darasati al-Qur'ān al-Karīm* (Beirut: Dār al-Jīl, 1992), 122–51.

⁸ Abū Maṣṣūr al-Māturīdī, *Tafsīr Tā'wīlāt Ahl al-Sunnah* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyyah, 2012), 1:349.

⁹ Ahmad Choirul Rofiq, "The methodology of al-maturidi's Qur'anic exegesis: Study of Ta'wilat Ahl al-sunnah", *Al-Jami'ah: Journal of Islamic Studies* 47, no. 2 (December 20, 2009): 323, doi:10.14421/ajis.2009.472.317-342. On *tafsīr* and *ta'wīl*, see: Abdul-Raof, *Schools of Qur'anic Exegesis*, 84-110. On *tafsīr bi-lRā'y*, see: Abdul-Raof, *Theological approaches to Qur'anic exegesis*, 28-82. Al-Baghdādī, *Ibid*, 7-9.

¹⁰ On juristic *tafsīr*, see: Abdul-Raof, *Schools of Qur'anic Exegesis*, 209-221.

¹¹ For a reassessment of al-Ṭabarī and al-Māturīdī and earliest *tafsīr* genres, see: Walid A. Saleh, "Rereading al-ṭabarī through al-māturīdī: New light on the Third century Hijrī", *Journal of Qur'anic Studies* 18, no. 2 (June 2016), doi:10.3366/jqs.2016.0242.

The exegesis of verse 4:34 by Abu al-Ḥassan al-Māwardī¹²

<p>The Exalted's statement: {Men are the maintainers of women} meaning the people of providing livelihood (<i>Ahl al-Qiyām</i>)¹³ are above their women [in authority concerning] disciplinary punishment (<i>tādībahunna</i>)¹⁴, and the taking of their hands [in marriage]¹⁵, in what God made obligatory for them [males] on them [women].¹⁶</p> <p>{because God has made one of them excel the other} meaning in intellect (<i>al-^cAql</i>) and rational opinion (<i>al-Rā'y</i>)¹⁷.</p>	<p>قوله تعالى: {الرجال قوامون على النساء} يعني أهل قيام على نساءهم, في تأديبهن, والأخذ على أيديهن, فيما أوجب الله لهم عليهن.</p> <p>{بما فضل الله بعضهم على بعض} يعني في العقل والرأي.</p>
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¹² Abī al-Ḥassan al-Māwardī, *al-Nukat wa al-'Uyūn Tafsīr al-Māwardī* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyyah, 2012), 1:480-483.

¹³ By explaining *qawwāmūn* with *Ahl al-Qiyām* it explains *qawwāmūn*, a nominal noun (*khabr marfū^c*), with *qiyām*, a verbal noun (*masdar*) of form I of the verb *qāma*, which in combination with the preposition *c alā* refers to providing sustenance and livelihood, but the meaning is also extended to encompass custodianship and guardianship, as explained by being responsible for disciplining them, and the authority to marry them or marry them off. The term *qawwāmūn* has generally been understood as proving male guardianship (*waliyya*) and command (*musallīṭūn* or *al-Qiyām bi-l-Amr*) over women in matters of social interactions (*mu^camalāt*) and religious leadership (*imama*). Abū al-Layth al-Samarqandī, *Tafsīr al-Samarqandī aw Baḥr al-^cUlūm* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'ilmiyya, 1993), 1:299. Ibn Jarīr al-Ṭabarī, *Jāmi^c al-Bayān fī Tā'wīl al-Qur'ān aw Tafsīr al-Ṭabarī* (Beirut: Mu'assasat al-Risāla, 2000), 8:290-291. Fakhr al-dīn al-Rāzī, *al-Tafsīr al-Kabīr aw Maḥāṭib al-Ghayb* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyyah, 2009), 10:72.

¹⁴ *Tādībahunna* is a verbal noun of form II of the verb *adab*, and refers to the transfer of good manners, etiquette, culture, and decency, through education and chastisement. Muḥammad Thanā' Allāh al-Maẓharī, *al-Tafsīr al-Maẓharī* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyyah, 2007), 2:91.

¹⁵ Although the Sunni *Fiqh* schools differed on the details, they all distinguished between immature or mature virgin women (*bikr*) who are dependent on a male guardian (*walī*) as a mediator for marriage proposals (although the Ḥanafī deemed the marriage of a mature virgin women without a guardian as permissible), and mature non-virgin women (*ayyim* or *thayyib*) who are deemed their own guardians. For a discussion on this, see: Susan Spector, *Women in classical Islamic law: A survey of the sources* (Netherlands: Brill Academic Publishers, 2009), 63–71, 148–151. Wahba al-Zuhaylī, *al-Fiqh al-Islamiyyu wa Adilatuhu* (Damascus: Dar al-Fikr, 2012), 9:6690 – 6717.

¹⁶ This sentence is taken from al-Ṭabarī with only a small adaption in the ending: Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:290.

¹⁷ *cAql* is generally viewed as the natural capability to perceive (*idrāk*) something and understand (*fahm*) it, from which a viewpoint (*rā'y*) of it can be formed. This part of verse 4:34 is generally used as a proof for the ontological difference between male female. Some scholars only mention, as is also mentioned by al-Māturīdī below, that this excelling is only in matters of inheritance (as stated clearly in the verses previous to it, 4:31-33) and providing income as is also stated directly by the verse itself, thereby seemingly rejecting any major ontological differences. But the majority of scholars go beyond the explanation provided by the verse by mentioning the difference in reason and opinion, which is sometimes used as a reason why women cannot be a *mujtahid*, independent jurist, which is also why they cannot be amcaliph. But several scholars accepted the possibility of women being *mujtahid* and even a judge (as stated by the Ḥanafī and Hanbali). And there are several scholars who also use this verse to mention a whole list of matters in which men supposedly excel over women to emphasize the ontological difference. A great example of this is the early modern Ḥanafī scholar Mullājiyūn al-Hanafī (d. 1718CE/1130AH) who mentions a whole list of things in which men excel women: Reason, resolution, firmness, archery, strength, fighting, to be able to fast and pray the whole month of Ramadan (i.e. not being interrupted by the monthly period), prophethood, being a caliph or imam, to perform the *Adhan*, to be a preacher, to be obligated to pray the Friday prayer in the mosque, to

<p>{and because men spend (<i>anfaqūā</i>) of their wealth (<i>amwālihim</i>) on them} meaning with it the dower (<i>al-Ṣadāq</i>)¹⁸ and the providing of livelihood through capability (<i>al-Qiyām bi-lKifāyah</i>).¹⁹</p>	<p>{وَبِمَا أَنْفَقُوا مِنْ أَمْوَالِهِمْ} يعني به الصداق والقيام بالكفاية.</p>
<p>And Jarīr bin Ḥāzm relates on al-Ḥassan that the reason (<i>sabab</i>) [of occasion of this verse] is that a man from the Helpers (<i>al-Anṣār</i>) slapped his wife and so she came to search for retaliation (<i>al-Qiṣās</i>)²⁰, so the Prophet (<i>ṣaws</i>)²¹ made retaliation [permissible] between them and then [this verse] was sent down: {And make no haste to recite the Qur'ān before its revelation is completed to you. (20:114)} and [then another] was sent down {Men are the maintainers of women because God has made one of them excel the other}²², and al-Zuhrī says: There is no retaliation between the man and his wife in anything except [in the case of taking] life.²³</p> <p>{So virtuous women (<i>al-ṣaliḥāt</i>) are those who are obedient (<i>qānitāt</i>) and guard in the</p>	<p>وقد روى جرير بن حازم عن الحسن أن سبب ذلك أن رجلاً من الأنصار لطم امرأته فجاءت تلتمس القصاص، فجعل النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم بينهما القصاص فنزلت: {ولا تعجل بالقرآن من قبل أن يقضى إليك وحيه} [طه: ١١٤] ونزلت {الرجال قوامون على النساء بما فضل الله بعضهم على بعض} وكان الزهري يقول: ليس بين الرجل وامرأته قصاص فيما دون النفس.</p>

be a witness in court, inheritance, to have the initiative in marriage and divorce, that the bloodline goes through the male, to grow a beard and wear a turban (i.e. to imitate the Prophet), and to be the source of income for the household. Mullājīyūn al-Hanafī (d. 1130/1718), *al-Tafsīrāt al-Aḥmadiyyah fī Bayān al-Ayāt al-Shar'īyyah* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyyah, 2010), pp. 182. A similar list is stated by Muḥammad Thanā' Allāh al-Mazharī (d. 1810CE/1225AH) where he says these differences are through difference in ontological disposition (*aṣl al-Khilqa*). Al-Mazharī, *Ibid*. See also: Majd al-Dīn al-Fayrūzābādī, *Tanwīr al-Miqbās min Tafsīr Ibn 'Abbās* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyyah, 2008), 91. Al-Rāzī, *Ibid*, 10:71-72. Wahba al-Zuhaylī, *al-Tafsīr al-Munīr fī al-'Aqīdah wa al-Sharī'ah wa al-Minhaj* (Damascus: Dār al-Fikr, 2003), 5:57.

¹⁸ *Ṣadāq* and *Mahr* are used as synonyms for bridal dowry. The bridal dowry's amount must be stipulated in the marriage contract. Spectorsky, *Ibid*, 82–85, 153–154.

¹⁹ *Kifāyah* refers to that which suffices and is appropriate to perform the required duty within one's capability. In Islamic law, the husband is obligated to provide housing, food and clothing for wife and children, insofar he is able. Not being able to provide an appropriate livelihood can be an acceptable reason for divorce, as spenditure is the right of the wife. Also a woman can stipulate a minimum of spenditure in her marriage contract. Spectorsky, *Ibid*, 82–85, 179–183. Al-Zuhaylī, *Ibid*, 9:6749.

²⁰ Retaliation in the case of bodily harm or murder is stipulated in Qur'ān 5:45 and 2:178-179.

²¹ Abbreviation for the customary Arabic blessing on the prophet: *ṣalli Allah alayhi wa salam* (blessings of God upon him and peace).

²² This is the occasion of revelation (*sabab al-Nuzūl*) which has been cited by the majority of Sunni exegetes on this verse. Al-Zuhaylī, *al-Tafsīr al-Munīr*, 5:57. Al-Samarqandī, *Ibid*. Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*. Chaudhry, *Ibid*, 29-39.

²³ This citation from the second generation (*tabi'*) scholar Ibn Shihāb al-Zuhrī (d. 741CE/124AH) is directly taken from al-Ṭabarī: *Ibid*, 8:292. This rule became standard among the Sunni schools that no official retaliation between spouses exist in the case of bodily harm, but only in the case of murder. Abū Ishāq al-Tha'labī, *al-Kashaf wa al-Bayān fī Tafsīr al-Qur'ān* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyyah, 2004), 2:279. But Islamic courts did punish spousal abuse and bodily mutilation through blood-money (*diya*) and as sufficient reason for female engaged divorce (*khul'*). For more on this, see: Hina Azam, *Sexual Violation in Islamic Law: Substance, Evidence, and Procedure* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 19. Brown, *Ibid*. Chaudhry, *Ibid*, 122.

<p>absence, in what God has guarded } meaning upholders of the religion (<i>al-Mustaqīmāt al-Dīn</i>) [and] acts (<i>al-ʿĀmilāt</i>)²⁴ in correctness (<i>bi-lKhayr</i>)²⁵, and the obedient (<i>qānitāt</i>)²⁶ means the obedient (<i>al-Muṭiyʿāt</i>) to God and their husbands.</p>	<p>{فالصالحات قانتات حافظات للغيب بما حفظ الله} يعني المستقيمات الدين العاملات بالخير, والقانتات يعني المطيعات لله ولأزواجهن.</p>
<p>{guardians of the absence (<i>ḥāfīzāt li-lGhayb</i>)²⁷} meaning the guarding of themselves in the absence of their husbands, and of what God has made obligatory of [the husband's] right on them.²⁸</p> <p>{in what God has guarded} in it are two statements: First: meaning God guards for them [women] because it induces them likewise [to guard], and it is a statement of ʿAṭā'.²⁹ Secondly: in what God has made obligatory on their husbands from their dowries and their expenses so they will start to guard it, and this is the statement of al-Zajāj. And ibn al-Mubārak relates on Saʿīd ibn Abī Saʿīd [that] Abī Hurayrah said: The Messenger of God said (saws): (Women are good wives when they look for what pleases you, and when you order her she obeys you, and when you're absent she guards you in her wealth and person) then the</p>	<p>{حافظات للغيب} يعني حافظات لأنفسهن عند غيبة أزواجهن, ولما أوجبه الله من حقه عليهن.</p> <p>{بما حفظ الله} فيه قولان: أحدهما: يعني يحفظ الله لهن إذ صيرهن كذلك, وهو قول عطاء. والثاني: بما أوجبه الله على أزواجهن من مهورهن ونفقتهن حتى صرن بها محفوظات, وهذا قول الزجاج. وقد روى ابن المبارك, سعيد بن أبي سعيد أبي هريرة قال: قال رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم: (خير النساء امرأة إذا نظرت إليها سرتك, وإذا أمرتها أطاعتك, وإذا غبت عنها حفظتك في مالها ونفسها) قال ثم قرأ رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم: {الرجال قوامون على النساء} إلى آخر الآية.</p>

²⁴ This explanation is also from al-Ṭabarī, but his editor has placed a comma between *al-Dīn* and *al-ʿĀmilāt* so it reads as separate sentences (i.e. upholders of the religion, and acts in goodness), which is also the reading I have upheld here. Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:293.

²⁵ *Khayr* refers to something good, excellent and admirable. I have translated it here as 'correctness' as I believe it here refers to something which is done in the best and correct way.

²⁶ *Qānitāt* is a feminine plural noun from the verb *qanata*, which means to be obedient, to perform something for a long period such as extensive religious prayers or pilgrimages. In the Qur'ān it is used for all of creation, male and female, who are obedient to God's will and devoted to Him (e.g. 2:116/238, 3:17/43, 16:120, 30:26, 33:31/35, 39:9, 66:5/12). In all these verses, the obedience is only to God, except for verse 33:31 which is directed to the Prophet's wives and refers to obedience to God and His messenger. It is this verse which is used to extend the meaning of *qānitāt* to encompass obedience to God and husband, although some scholars state that the Prophet's wives are a special category whereby verse 33:31 is specific (*khass*) to them alone. Edward William Lane, *Arabic-English Lexicon* (Beirut: Librairie Du Liban, 1968), 1:2566 – 2567. Al-Zuhaylī, *al-Tafsīr al-Munīr*, 22:6. Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:294. Abū Bakr al-Rāzī al-Jaṣṣāṣ, *Ahkām Al-Qur'ān* (Beirut: Dār ihyā' al-Turāth al-ʿArabiyya, 1985), 5:229. Al-Māturīdī, *Ibid*, 8:379. Al-Rāzī, *Ibid*, 10:72.

²⁷ This is part of the verse is one of the least clear in the intended meaning. The noun *ghayb* is used 49 times in the Qur'ān, whereby they all but this verse refer to the metaphysical unseen world of which only God has knowledge. This verse is therefore understood to be the only one using *ghayb* in a secular sense. *Ḥāfīzāt* is a feminine plural noun, but most translations translate it into a verb (i.e. guarding). *Ḥāfīzāt* comes from the verb *ḥafīza* and means to protect or preserve something against loss or harm. "English translations of 4:34", accessed augustus 14, 2016, <http://www.islamawakened.com/quran/4/34/default.htm>.

²⁸ The majority of classical scholars understood the *ghayb* to refer to guarding her chastity and the property her husband spends on her, as the former is his right on her through the latter. Al-Rāzī, *Ibid*, 10:72.

²⁹ Two explanations are provided for in what way God has also guarded. The first meaning related from the *tabi' ʿAṭā'* ibn Abī Rabāḥ (d. 733CE/114AH) seemingly refers to her chastity, as God has protected her against harm, so must she protected herself against sin (i.e. adultery). Taken from Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:296.

<p>Messenger of God (saws) recited: {Men are the maintainers of women} towards the end of the verse.³⁰</p>	
<p>{As from those women you fear ill-conduct} in {fear} has two interpretations: First: That it is knowledge (<i>al-ilm</i>)³¹, which is expressed through fear, such as the poet said: (And you do not bury me in the open desert so that I ... fear (<i>akhāf</i>) when I possibly (<i>mā</i>) die that I don't experience it) meaning so that I know, and the second interpretation: that it is speculation (<i>al-Zann</i>)³², as said by the poet (It comes to me on a victorious word through his saying ... and what I fear O peacefulness (<i>salām</i>) is that you are my defect³³) and is that it covers over her ill-conduct with what shows her bad act.³⁴</p> <p>And ill-conduct (<i>al-Nushūz</i>): is disobedience to the husband³⁵ and the refusal of obeying him through hatred and disgust - and the root of <i>al-Nushūz</i> is: the rising (<i>al-irtifā'</i>), and from it it is said of the risen place (<i>lil-makān al-Murtafi'</i>) is risen (<i>nashaza</i>) from the ground³⁶, so you name the abstaining from her husband as a disobedience (<i>nāshizā</i>) of her distancing from him [in conjugal relations] and her rising against him [in what he asks of her].³⁷</p>	<p>{واللاتي تخافون نشوزهن} في {تخافون} تأويلان: أحدهما: أنه العلم , فعبر عنه بالخوف , كما قال الشاعر: (ولا تدفني بالقبلة فأني ... أخاف إذا ما مت أن لا ادوقها) يعني فأني أعلم، والتأويل الثاني: أنه الظن , كما قال الشاعر: (أتاني عن نصر كلام بقوله ... وما خفت يا سلام أنك عائبي) وهو أن يستر على نشوزها بما تبديه من سوء فعلها.</p> <p>والنشوز: هو معصية الزوج والامتناع من طاعته بغضا وكراهة - وأصل النشوز: الارتفاع , ومنه قيل للمكان المرتفع من الأرض نشز , فسميت الممتنعة عن زوجها ناشزا لبعدها منه وارتفاعها عنه.</p>
<p>{you may admonish them and [then] abandon them in their beds with them and beat them} as for admonishing her it is that you command her through the fear (<i>taqwā</i>) of God and obedience to Him, and you frighten her</p>	<p>{فعضون واهجروهن في المضاجع واضربوهن} أما وعظها فهو أن يأمرها بتقوى الله وطاعته , ويخوفها استحقاق الوعيد في معصيته وما أباحه الله تعالى من ضربها عند مخالفته , وفي المراد بقوله: {واهجروهن في المضاجع} خمسة أقاويل: أحدها: ألا يجامعها , وهو قول ابن عباس , وسعيد بن جبير.</p>

³⁰ The second meaning related from the Qur'ān scholar Abū Ishāq al-Zajāj (d. 923CE/311AH), author of one of the earliest linguistic *tafsīr* works, *Ma'ānī al-Qur'ān*, refers to why she would guard it specifically for her husband; he earned it by paying her a dowry and provides livelihood. This second meaning is then strengthened by a Ḥadīth where a wife's pleasing, obedience, and guarding is linked to the husband's spending wealth in her. Abū Ishāq al-Zajāj, *Ma'ānī al-Qur'ān* (Beirut: ʿĀlam al-Kutub, 1988), 2:47. Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:295. See also al-Maḥḥarī, *Ibid*, 2:92.

³¹ *ilm*, knowledge, is placed here as opposite to *zann*, speculation. The fear must therefore be based on certain knowledge, i.e. proof by witness. The ill-conduct is understood here as referring to adultery. Meaning a husband can only apply the three admonitions when he has proof by witnessing himself, or by others, that she has committed adultery (*zinā*) or indecency (*fāḥisha*), and not simple spousal disobedience. Al-Maḥḥarī, *Ibid*, 2:93.

³² In this interpretation, a husband can apply the three admonitions based on speculation of adultery.

³³ *Salām* also means 'to be free of defects', and is clearly used in this double meaning whereby his mind is at ease, free of the defect of suspicion, and it is exactly this which could be his true defect.

³⁴ This whole part is taken from al-Ṭabarī. Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:295. For discussions on all the meanings related to *khawf*, see: Chaudhry, *Ibid*, 58-61.

³⁵ And therefore the opposite behaviour of *Qānitāt* women.

³⁶ This is the first time a word is explained through linguistics (*luḡha*) instead of commentary (*tafsīr*) or semantic analogy through poetry.

³⁷ For a discussion on all the meanings related to *nushūz*, see: Chaudhry, *Ibid*, 62-67.

<p>[with] the deserved [eschatological] threat³⁸ in disobeying Him, and [frighten her also with that] God the Exalted allowed him in hitting her at the instant of offense to him (<i>min ḍarabhā 'indi mukhālaftahī</i>)³⁹, and the intent in His statement: {and leave them in the beds} there are five statements: first: desist from having sex with her, and it is the statement of Ibn 'Abbās, and Sa'īd bin Jabīr. And secondly: that you do not speak to her and devote [attention] to her in the afternoon in bed, and is a statement of al-Ḍaḥāk, and al-Sadī. And thirdly: That you leave her bed and [abstain from having] intercourse with her and is [also] a statement from al-Ḍaḥāk, and al-Sadī. Fourthly: meaning and you say to them in the beds 'separation (<i>hijrā</i>)⁴⁰, and [this] is viscously spoken, and this is a statement of 'Akramah, and al-Ḥassan. And fifthly: it is what is tied when abandoned and is a rope you tie to the camel for it to stay during intercourse [with another camel]⁴¹, and this is a statement of Abī J'afar al-Ṭabarī.</p>	<p>والثاني: أن لا يكلمها ويوليها ظهره في المضجع , وهو قول الضحاك , والسدي. والثالث: أن يهجر فراشها ومضاجعتها وهو قول الضحاك , والسدي. والرابع: يعني وقولوا لهن في المضجع هجرا , وهو الإغلاظ في القول , وهذا قول عكرمة , والحسن. والخامس: هو أن يربطها بالهجار وهو حبل يربط به البعير ليقرها على الجماع , وهو قول أبي جعفر الطبري.</p>
<p>And it is interfered through the tradition of Ibn al-Mubārak on Bahz bin Ḥakīm on his father on his grandfather who said: I said O Messenger of God how should we approach our wives and how should we leave them? He said: (Approach your tilth when or how you will⁴², desist from beating her face and do not revile her except in the house, that you give her food when you have food yourself, and that you clothe her when you clothe yourself, how I inform some of you to some others) and in this tradition there is no proof on any other interpretation. And the root of abandoning (<i>al-Hajr</i>): leaving it</p>	<p>واستدل برواية ابن المبارك عن بهز بن حكيم عن أبيه عن جده قال: قلت يا رسول الله نساؤنا ما نأتي منها وما نذر؟ قال: (حرتك فأت حرتك أنى شئت غير ألا تضرب الوجه ولا تقبح إلا في البيت , وأطعم إذا طعمت واكس إذا اكتسيت , كيف وقد أفضى بعضكم إلى بعض) وليس في هذا الخبر دليل على تأويله دون غيره. وأصل الهجر: الترك على قلى , والهجر: القبيح من القول لأنه مهجور.</p>

³⁸ *Al-Wa'īd* means the threat or promise, and used for an worldly or eschatological divine punishment, as in Qur'ān 14:14, 20:113, 50:14. For a discussion on all the meanings related to admonishment, see: Chaudhry, *Ibid*, 68-70.

³⁹ I understand the *min* here to be linked to frightening her, and the *'indi* as referring to a causal link, meaning *with the moment his rights are violated by her, he is allowed to hit her*. The three admonitions can be read as consecutive or not, depending on if the conjunction *wa* (and) is read as connecting without sequence (*al-Jami' al-Muṭlaq*) or as providing a condition which denotes a sequence (*al-Ḥāl*) and is read as 'then'. Nizām al-Dīn al-Shāshī, *Uṣūl al-Shāshī ma'a Iḥsan al-Ḥawāshī* (Karachi: Maktabah al-Bushrā, 2008), 125–126. See also: Chaudhry, *Ibid*, 103. Al-Rāzī, *Ibid*, 10:73-74.

⁴⁰ Probably meaning that *hijra* is said to the wife as a warning that a real separation, divorce, is imminent.

⁴¹ This is the second time a linguistic meaning is provided for a word, and which here provides an opposite meaning: a way to make her not leave. And indirectly can be understood as that the couple is not allowed to leave the bedrooms until they had intercourse. If this is meant as allowing marital rape, or trying to seduce her to have intercourse by her own will, is left open. Conjugal relations were seen as the right of the husband which she provided him through the marriage, and which therefore is sinful to deny him. The majority of scholars clearly disliked the idea of forced intercourse, but did not see it as criminal. For more on this, see: Azam, *Ibid*. Chaudhry, *Ibid*, 71-79, 88, 104-105.

⁴² Referring to Qur'ān 2:223.

detested, and <i>al-Hajr</i> : the reviled from the statement because it is an abandoned thing	
<p>{and beat them (<i>aḍribūhunna</i>)⁴³} thus God the Exalted makes punishing her for ill-conduct [in] three things: and admonish her and abandon her and beat her. And in regulating her (<i>turattabīhā</i>) when she has ill-conduct [there] are two statements: firstly: that when ill-conduct is feared and she is admonished and abandoned, [after these steps are taken] that she establishes [the last option] on him to hit her. And secondly: that when her ill-conduct is feared and she is admonished, so when the ill-conduct starts abandon her, so that she establishes [the option] on him to hit her, and it is the most apparent meaning (<i>al-Azhar</i>) from the statement of Shāfi'ī.⁴⁴ And which permits him [to apply] the beating as chastisement (<i>tādībā</i>) [as a form of] rebuking her for the ill-conduct [but must be] without violence (<i>ghayri mubarriḥ</i>) and no cruelty (<i>lā munhik</i>).⁴⁵ Bashir relates on</p>	<p>{وأضربوهن} فجعل الله تعالى معاقبتها على النشوز ثلاثة أشياء: وعظها وهجرها وضربها. وفي ترتيبها إذا نشزت قولان: أحدهما: أنه إذا خاف نشوزها وعظها وهجرها , فإن أقامت عليه ضربها. والثاني: أنه إذا خاف نشوزها وعظها , فإذا أبدت النشوز هجرها , فإن أقامت عليه ضربها , وهو الأظهر من قول الشافعي. والذي أبيع له من الضرب ما كان تأديبا يزجرها به عن النشوز غير مبرح ولا منك , روى بشر عن عكرمة قال: قال رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم: (اضربوهن إذا عصيتم في المعروف ضربا غير مبرح).</p>

⁴³ The word *aḍribūhunna* is a 2nd person masculine plural imperative from the verb *daraba*. This verb has many meanings, and several modernists attempts to apply different meanings apart from hitting (the most common alternative interpretation being ‘leave them completely’) have the problem that these alternatives need a prefix according to general linguistic understanding. According to an anonymous study which surveys the Qur’ānic use of the verb and the different ways it is portrayed in early dictionaries, the verb can only mean ‘hitting’ or ‘striking’ when an object is involved that does the striking. This interesting observation would explain why: women must ‘strike’ their covers over themselves and not ‘strike’ with their feet in 24:31; Moses ‘striking’ the sea and rock with his staff in 2:60, 7:160, and 26:63; the murdered person must be ‘hit’ with a part of a sacrificed cow in 2:73; and Job ‘striking’ it with a bundle of reed in 38:44. When ‘striking’ alone is used in other verses, it is mostly understood to be with an object: the ‘hitting’ of the statues by Abraham in 37:93 is explained as striking with an axe; ‘striking’ the necks in 8:12 and 47:4 is explained as striking with a sword. “Wife beating in islam? The Quran strikes back!”, accessed august 15, 2016, <http://www.quran434.com/wife-beating-islam.html>. This fact would explain why several *Aḥādīth* and related opinions by prophetic companions say the ‘hitting’ in 4:34 means hitting with a handkerchief or a small stick such as the toothstick (*siwāk*) due to the fact that the verb *daraba* in general means hitting with an object and not hitting empty handed. Al-Tha’labī, *Ibid*, 2:280. Abū Bakr al-Rāzī al-Jaṣṣāṣ, *Aḥkām al-Qur’ān* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-‘Ilmiyyah, 2003), 2:237 – 238. Although this online study shows is that *aḍribūhunna* in 4:34 can still mean hitting empty handed, it does correctly point out that the Qur’ān could have used other synonyms (such as the verb *laṭama* as is used in the forementioned *sabab*, see fn. 21 above) which would have left no doubt that physical hitting with the hand was meant. For a discussion on the different meanings proposed by traditional and modern interpreters related to the verb *daraba*, see: Chaudhry, *Ibid*, 80-92, 95-128.

⁴⁴ Here the literal meaning is understood to mean not that when the ill-conduct starts, the abandoning starts and the option of hitting is immediately also allowed, and seen as self-provoked. Here is also the only time that al-Māwardī shows his school affiliation (i.e. the Shāfi’ītes). His tafsīr on this verse is approached mainly from a non-*Fiqhi* perspective while al-Māturīdī on the other hand clearly discusses it from within a Ḥanafī framework.

⁴⁵ *Mubarriḥ* is a noun from the verb *bariḥa*, and refers to intense and tormenting violence. *Munhik* from *nahaka* refers to enduring something grueling and exhausting. So the *ghayri* indicates what the hitting must lack, and the *lā* indicates when the hitting must end. The condition ‘without violence’ is repeated by almost all commentators, as this is the term clearly stated in the majority of *Aḥādīth*, but multiple second conditions are mentioned apart from *munhik* such as *shāqq* (hardship) or *shā’n* (disgrace) or *kāsir* (breaking bones) or

<p>°Akramah saying: The Messenger of God (saws) said (Beat them when they resist you in the accepted good, [but] beat without violence (<i>ghayri mubarraḥ</i>)).⁴⁶</p> <p>{If they, then, obey you, you shall seek no other way against them} meaning they obey you in the bed and directly. {you shall seek no other way against them} in it are two interpretations: firstly: Do not seek to injure them. And secondly: is that he says to her 'you do not love me and you refuse me', which induces her [to not refuse him] and that she is obedient: Sufyān said: when she does that she is not responsible for loving him because her heart is not in her hand [i.e. control].⁴⁷</p>	<p>{فإن أطعنكم فلا تبغوا عليهن سبيلا} يعني أطعنكم في المضجع والمباشرة. {فلا تبغوا عليهن سبيلا} فيه تأويلان: أحدهما: لا تطلبوا لهن الأذى. والثاني: هو أن يقول لها لست تحبينني وأنت تعصيني، فيصيرها على ذلك وإن كانت مطيعة: قال سفيان: إذا فعلت ذلك لا يكلفها أن تحبه لأن قلبها ليس في يدها.</p>
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The exegesis of verse 4:34 by Abu Manṣūr al-Māturīdī⁴⁸

<p>The people of interpretation (<i>Ahl al-Tā'wīl</i>)⁴⁹ say (<i>qāl</i>): The verse was revealed [concerning] husbands; its proof is the Exalted His statement: {and in what they spend (<i>anfaqūā</i>) of their wealth (<i>amwālihum</i>)} and the husbands are the takers [in marriage] of their spouses by [providing] expenditure [thereby gaining rights over her], and this is the proof that expenditure for the wife is an obligation (<i>wujūb</i>) on her</p>	<p>قال أهل التأويل: الآية نزلت في الأزواج؛ دليله قوله - تعالى - : (وبما أنفقوا من أموالهم) والأزواج هم المأخوذون بنفقة أزواجهم، وفيه دليل وجوب نفقة المرأة على زوجها، وعلى ذلك إجماع أهل العلم.</p>
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khādish (scratching). Al-Tha'labī, *Ibid*. Al-Fayrūzābādī, *Ibid*. Chaudhry, *Ibid*, 232-233. Isma'il Ḥaqqī al-Burūsawī, *Rūḥ al-Bayān fī Tafsīr al-Qur'ān* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyyah, 2013), 2:207.

⁴⁶ Although prophetic *Aḥādīth* exist which state that hitting women is not allowed (which are cited by al-Māturīdī below), it are versions similar to this *Ḥadīth* which are mostly cited as Sunna-explanations of this verse which only restricts the hitting in intensity or location (not the face, arms etc.). For an overview of traditions, see: Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:311-316. Al-Zuhaylī, *al-Tafsīr al-Munīr*, 5:60-61. Chaudhry, *Ibid*.

⁴⁷ Meaning he can only demand general obedience, but he cannot demand that she loves him. Taken from: Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:317.

⁴⁸ Al-Māturīdī, *Ibid*, 3:156-165. I have followed the Dār al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyyah sentence structure, although the Turkish Dār al-Mīzān (see fn. 58 below) has a better structure, as the latter only became available to me halfway this paper.

⁴⁹ Both al-Māturīdī and al-Ṭabarī use *ta'wīl* as a title for their tafsīr works, whereby they both refer to 'the people of interpretation (*Ahl al-Tā'wīl*)' as an indication for the Qur'ān scholars, jurists, and grammarians among the early generations (*al-Salaf*) and the fourth and later generations (*al-Khalaf*), with the exception that al-Māturīdī also includes the theologians.

<p>husband⁵⁰, and on that is a consensus (<i>ijmā'</i>) of the people of knowledge (<i>Ahl al-ilm</i>).⁵¹</p> <p>And some of the people of knowledge (<i>Ahl al-ilm</i>) said (<i>qāl</i>) that in the Exalted His statement: {Men are the maintainers of women} is the proof that marriage is not permitted except with [the consent and cooperation of] a guardian (<i>bi-lWalī</i>), due to the fact that it informs [us] that they [men] are the maintainers of them [women] with or without them.⁵²</p> <p>It is said (<i>qīl</i>) of [guardianship by the Ḥanafī]: The verse concerns [both] husbands and guardians on what is mentioned [above, i.e. obligation to provide expenditure] therefore in [this fact] itself is proof that marriage without a guardian is permitted and doesn't nullify it.⁵³</p>	<p>وقال بعض أهل العلم في قوله - تعالى - : (الرجال قوامون على النساء) - دليل ألا يجوز النكاح إلا بالولي، حيث أخبر أنهم القوامون عليهن دونهن.</p> <p>قيل له: إن كانت الآية في الأزواج وفي الأولياء على ما ذكرت ففيه دليل جواز النكاح بغير ولي لا بطلانه،</p>
<p>And that the Exalted says: {Men are the maintainers of women because God has made one of them excel the other} expressing that some of them excel others, and that the ones excelling have an excelling disposition (<i>khilqa</i>)⁵⁴, and the male is created as the people of labour and commerce (<i>Ahl al-Makāsib wa al-Tajārāt</i>)⁵⁵, and the providing in livelihood (<i>al-</i></p>	<p>وذلك قوله - تعالى - : (الرجال قوامون على النساء بما فضل الله بعضهم على بعض) أخبر أنه فضل بعضهم على بعض، وذلك التفضيل تفضيل خلقية، وهو أن جعل الرجال من أهل المكاسب والتجارات، والقيام بأنواع الحرف، والتقلب في البلدان والمدائن، والنساء ليس كذلك؛ بل جعلهن ضعفاء عاجزات عن القيام بالمكاسب والحرف والتقلب في حاجاتهن؛ فالرجال هم القوامون عليهن. والون أمورهن، وقاضون حوائجنهن، قائمون على ذلك،</p>

⁵⁰ See also fn. 13 and 19 above.

⁵¹ The people of knowledge (*Ahl al-ilm*) refer to the jurists among the early (*al-Salaf*) and later generations (*al-Khalaf*) of Muslim scholars who can formulate majority and consensus opinions.

⁵² The Mālikī, Shāfi'ī, and Ḥanbalī schools all state every [unmarried] female must have a male guardian over them, who arranges her marriage contract, and in the case of male and female orphans, also arranges their finances and inheritance. This guardian is generally a male relative, but when these are not available a judge or ruler can act as a guardian. See: Sectorsky, *Ibid*, 63-71, 148-151.

⁵³ The Ḥanafī differ on this matter as they view a guardian as only an obligation in the case of minors, insane and orphans, but only preferred with mature women. If a mature woman wants to marry a man who is her equal (*kafā'a*) in status, then a guardian is not necessary. Interestingly enough, the Samarqandī school of the Ḥanafī disagreed on this with the rest of the Ḥanafī, which is maybe why al-Māturīdī uses *qīl* (it is said) here as this designates a weaker or minority opinion. Although it is clear from his commentary on this verse that al-Māturīdī sides with the majority of the Ḥanafī against the obligation of guardianship. On the Ḥanafī position towards guardianship, see: Sectorsky, *Ibid*, 70-71, 75-78.

⁵⁴ Al-Māturīdī also sees the excelling over another referring to ontological differences, but only in relation to bodily differences and the hardship of labour and long-distance trade. As discussed below at fn. 62, if the husband becomes chronologically ill he has the same incapable disposition as the female to earn money through labour. It is therefore clear that al-Māturīdī doesn't view the gender differences in disposition as non-interchangeable, i.e. the male excel over women just for being male. To al-Māturīdī the excelling is directly related to differences in bodily strength and therefore only concerns the incapability of hard labour and long-distance trade. He does mention that some say this refers to a difference in reason and inheritance, but he designates this as a weaker or minority opinion by using *qīl* (it is said). Stronger or majority opinions he designates with *qāl*. See also fn. 57 and 63 below.

⁵⁵ *Makāsib* comes from the verb *kasaba*, meaning to earn or acquire something, which refers to earning money through trade or labour. I understand it here as referring to hard labour as it mentioned as a parallel to long-distance trade. In verse 4:32 it used for any form of earning done by men or women. *Tajārāt* is a plural noun from *tajara* which refers to trading, and is mentioned in verse 4:29. Al-Māturīdī usually incorporates

<p><i>Qiyām</i>) is from the types of trade (<i>al-Hiraf</i>), and the fluctuation (<i>al-Taqallub</i>) [through travel] in countries and cities⁵⁶, and women don't do that; Rather they are created delicate (<i>ḍuʿafāʾ</i>) and incapable (<i>ʿājjizāt</i>)⁵⁷ to maintain their livelihood through earning and trade and fluctuation [of travel]; therefore men are maintainers for them. They [women] entrust (<i>wālūna</i>)⁵⁸ their affairs [to the men], and administrate their [women] goods, maintaining [these matters], thus [a duty which is] imposed on the men maintaining the livelihood in their [women's] welfare interests (<i>maṣāliḥahunna</i>)⁵⁹, as we mentioned with what is imposed on the male [of expenditure].</p> <p>It is permissible if they [women] entrust by themselves and maintaining their own goods with the merchants, and [maintain their own] purchases, and other [such things]⁶⁰; Therefore on the basis of the marriage, the men become maintainers for them [women], so that they [women] if they entrust by themselves and carry out [their own trade and purchases]- it is permissible as it is permissible for the other, and</p>	<p>ففرض على الرجال القيام بمصالحهن كما ذكرنا مع ما فرض ذلك على الرجال.</p> <p>يجوز إذا ولين بأنفسهن وقمن بحوائجهن من البياعات، والأشربية، وغير ذلك؛ فعلى ذلك النكاح، وإن كان الرجال هم القوام عليهن، فإنهن إذا ولين ذلك بأنفسهن وقمن - جاز ذلك كما جاز غيره، وكذا ما أمر الأولياء بالتزويج في قوله - تعالى -: (وأنكحوا الأيامى منكم. . . الآية)، ونهاهم عن العضل عن النكاح بقوله - عز وجل -: (فلا تعضلوهن أن ينكحن أزواجهن. . . الآية)؛ لأن ذلك حق عليهم أن يفعلوا حتى يلين ذلك بأنفسهن؛ إذ لا بد من حضور مشهود الرجال ومجلسهم ليشهدوا على ذلك، فذلك على الأولياء القيام به.</p>
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elements from other verses into his exegesis as a form of *tafsīr al-Qur'ān bi-lQur'ān*, exegesis of the Qur'ān through the Qur'ān itself. This exegetical methodology is more holistic and less atomistic.

⁵⁶ *Taqallub* is a noun of *qalaba* which refers to alternation and fluctuation, and here refers to the traveling up and down between cities and countries as done by caravans.

⁵⁷ The word *ḍuʿafāʾ* is a plural noun of *ḍaʿif* which refers to something weak, frail, delicate, or impotent. The word *ʿājjizāt* from the verb *ʿajaza* semantically overlaps with this as it refers to be to weak, powerless or incapable of performing something. The majority of exegetes, as stated above at fn. 17, used this verse to emphasize male superiority over women in bodily, cognitive and religious matters. Al-Māturīdī on the other hand only refers that women are not built for the difficult and dangerous travels needed to trade in medieval times.

⁵⁸ *Wālūna* is not the correct verb form from *waliya* (entrusting, charging over, guarding), it should be in the 3rd person active perfect tense verb *wālliyna*. The publisher of this edition, Dār al-Kutub al-ʿIlmiyya, did not correct the manuscript here. The more critical edition of al-Māturīdī's exegesis by the Turkish publisher Dār al-Mīzān has corrected the manuscript into *wālliyna*. Abū Maṣūʾir al-Māturīdī, *Tāʾwīlāt al-Qur'ān li-lAbū Maṣūʾir Muḥammad b. Muḥammad al-Māturīdī al-Samarqandī* (Istanbul: Dār al-Mīzān, 2005), 3:199.

⁵⁹ *Maṣāliḥ* is the plural of the Form I verbal noun *maṣlaḥa* from the verb *ṣāliḥa*, which refers to something which is good, useful, suitable, and makes something thrive. It is used as a technical term for the teleological pursuit for a person's or group's benefit and welfare in creation and/or revelation, see: Felicitas Opwis, *Maslaḥa and the purpose of the law: Islamic discourse on legal change from the 4th/10th to 8th/14th century* (Netherlands: Brill Academic Publishers, 2010), 9ff. Anver M. Emon, *Islamic natural law theories* (New York: Oxford University Press, USA, 2010), 45ff.

⁶⁰ The overall majority of scholars among the schools allow women to trade, buy and sell, whereby any earnings are their personal property (*māl*) (which is also mentioned in the previous verses 4:29-33). Therefore one would expect this female financial independence would be a normal subject mentioned in the discussions on male guardianship. But such nuanced discussion on guardianship, whereby the independent financial guardianship of women is mentioned to mirror and relativize the guardianship of the husband, is rare among exegetes (I dare to say even unique). We can therefore state that al-Māturīdī clearly refrains from seeing this verse as stating a complete dominance of men over women, or the complete dependency of the latter on the former, but instead sees this verse as only laying out the social duties on men which serve the interests of their women.

<p>such is what is commanded to the guardians by marrying off [those who he is in charge of] in the Exalted's statement -: {And marry off those single among you...(24:32)} [till the end of] the verse; And forbids them [men] from preventing the marriage [of women] through the statement of the Mighty and Majestic -: {Do not hinder them from [re-]marrying their husbands...(2:232)} [till the end of] the verse⁶¹; Because that is a right on them [men] that they act in order that they [women] can entrust by themselves; because it is inescapable (<i>lā budd min</i>) for the men attending (<i>ḥuḍūr</i>) the spectacle [i.e. the marriage] and their gathering to act as witnesses for [the marriage], so that is [the duty imposed] on the maintaining guardians.⁶²</p>	
<p>And such is what makes the women's expenditure if it is not for the women wealth (<i>al-Māl</i>) which is the women's inviolable [property] (<i>maḥārimhunna</i>)⁶³; Because they do not undertake labour and the types of trade and commerce, and men do undertake [this], so to create the women's provisions is on them [men as a duty]; For the women's delicateness and incapability to maintain a livelihood through labour is by disposition; Hence, what is not made by the males (<i>li-IDhukūr</i>) of the inviolable [property] is [what makes] some of them [excel] over some [others in] the expenditure; [Meaning:] for what he maintains through labour; So when he becomes chronically ill (<i>zaminā</i>) and is incapable to labour [this] would make his expenditure [belonging] to his own inviolable [property]; Because he has become in</p>	<p>وكهذا ما جعل نفقتهم إذا لم يكن لهم مال على محارمهن؛ لأنهن لا يقمن بالمكاسب وأنواع الحرف والتجارات، والرجال يقومون، فجعل مؤنتهن عليهم؛ لضعفهن وعجزهن عن القيام بالمكاسب خلقة؛ ولهذا ما لم يجعل للذكور من المحارم بعضهم على بعض النفقة؛ لما يقومون بالمكاسب؛ فإذا صار زمنا وعجز عن المكاسب جعل نفقته على محارمه؛ لأنه صار في الخلق كالمرأة، والله أعلم.</p>

⁶¹ Here al-Māturīdī links independent financial guardianship of women to their independence in choosing and arranging their own marriage, i.e. act as their own guardian. He ingeniously uses verses 24:32 and 2:232 to prove the independent guardianship of women which obligated the guardian to allow her to marry.

⁶² Here al-Māturīdī emphasizes that guardians are obligated to act as witnesses of the marriage. Marriages require two male witnesses and a guardian. Spectorsky, *Ibid*, 78-82.

⁶³ *Maḥārim* is a plural noun from *ḥaruma* referring to something which inviolable and forbidden. Here it refers to personal wealth which is inviolable for her husband to touch.

<p>disposition like a woman⁶⁴, and God knows best.⁶⁵</p> <p>And Ibn ʿAbbās - may God be pleased with him – said concerning His statement: {Men are the maintainers of women because God has made one of them excel the other}: “[As] rulers (<i>umarāʾ</i>) on them that they obey him in what God has commanded him from His demanded obedience, and His obedience is that she is charitable (<i>muḥsina</i>) towards her people, protecting his wealth, and he excels her through his expenditure and his capacity.”⁶⁶</p>	<p>وعن ابن عباس - رضي الله عنه - في قوله: (الرجال قوامون على النساء بما فضل الله بعضهم على بعض) قال: أمراء عليهن أن تطيعه فيما أمر الله به من طاعته، وطاعته أن تكون محسنة إلى أهلها، حافظة لماله، وفضله عليها بنفقته وسعته.</p>
<p>It is said (<i>qīl</i>): The verse was sent down when a man slapped his wife in her face; So she was recalcitrant to her husband in bed, and she appealed to the Messenger of God (<i>ṣaws</i>) and said: “O Messenger of God, my husband slapped me without [being] slapped”, and a trace of his hand was on her face; So the Messenger of God (<i>ṣaws</i>) said to her: “retaliate on him”, and retaliation was between them on that day between men and women in slapping (<i>al-Laṭma</i>), [causing] fracture (<i>al-Shajja</i>), and hitting (<i>al-Darba</i>), then the Prophet (<i>ṣaws</i>) saw Jibrīl – on him be peace – who revealed; So he said to her: “Stop until I see what part is with Jibrīl concerning your issue”, and so came this verse: {Men are the maintainers of women because God has made one of them excel the other}</p>	<p>وقيل: نزلت الآية في رجل لطم امرأته لكمة في وجهها؛ فنشزت عن فراش زوجها، واستعدت إلى رسول الله - صلى الله عليه وسلم - فقالت: يا رسول الله، لطمني زوجي فلان لكمة، وهذا أثر يده في وجهي؛ فقال لها رسول الله - صلى الله عليه وسلم -: " اقتصي منه "، وكان القصاص بينهم يومئذ بين الرجال والنساء في اللكمة والشجة والضربة، ثم أبصر النبي - صلى الله عليه وسلم - جبريل - عليه السلام - ينزل؛ فقال لها: " كفي حتى أنظر ما جاء به جبريل في أمرك "، فأتاه بهذه الآية: (الرجال قوامون على النساء بما فضل الله بعضهم على بعض) أي: المسلطون على آداب النساء في الحق.</p>

⁶⁴ Here al-Māturīdī distinguishes between a woman’s personal wealth such as the dower or that which she has inherited or earned herself, and what the husband spends on her. What he spends on her is not her personal wealth, and it his duty to create expenditure for her and it is only in this creating of expenditure that the one excels the other. In the moment the husband becomes chronically ill, he becomes just as incapable as the women to earn expenditure through labour, and technically his personal wealth would become inviolable too. As stated above, it is clear that al-Māturīdī doesn’t view the gender differences in disposition as non-interchangeable, whereby the male excel over women just for being male. It is directly related to differences in bodily strength and therefore only concerns the incapability of hard labour and long-distance trade. When this capability falls away, so does the excelling of him over her. Again such a nuanced discussion on gender differences is rare among classical and even modern exegetes. See also fn. 54 and 57 above. This does not mean that al-Māturīdī saw both genders as compatible for each role, as it is known al-Māturīdī rejects the possibility of female prophets, while the other foundational orthodox theologian al-Ashʿarī (d. 936CE/324AH) accepted the possibility. See: Ibn Kamāl al-Pāshā, *Risāla al-Ikhtilāf bayn al-Ashʿariyya wa al-Māturīdiyya*, point 11.

⁶⁵ The term “God knows best” is a direct indication that we are dealing here with *taʿwīl* and not *tafsīr*, as the former is based on one or multiple reasoned opinions which all could be possibly true whereby only God knows which one is truly true. This term is used for the accepted disagreement (*ikhtilāf*) among the later generations, and not for the differences in statements among the early generations which are generally not deemed as being based on reason but on prophetic teachings. See: Rofiq, *Ibid*, 328–329.

⁶⁶ Almost similar in wording to al-Ṭabarī. Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:290. This is one of the only statements from a prophetic companion used by al-Māturīdī in this verse. Al-Māturīdī’s exegesis contains few traditions from the Prophet or the early generation, and only uses a certain selection of companions and second generation scholars. See: Rofiq, *Ibid*, 327-328.

<p>meaning: Commanding (<i>musalliṭūn</i>) over the behaviour (<i>adāb</i>) of women in right (<i>al-Ḥaqq</i>).⁶⁷</p> <p>And it is said (<i>qīl</i>): They excel on them women in reason (<i>al-ʿAql</i>) and inheritance (<i>al-Mīrāth</i>), and in booty (<i>al-Faya</i>)⁶⁸, and God knows best.</p> <p>Then the Messenger of God (<i>ṣaws</i>) said: “We wanted something and God wanted something, and God wanted something better than what we wanted.”⁶⁹</p>	<p>وقيل: تفضيلهم عليهن بالعقل والميراث، وفي الفيء، والله أعلم.</p> <p>ثم قال رسول الله - صلى الله عليه وسلم -: " أردنا أمرا وأراد الله أمرا، والذي أراد الله خير مما أردنا "</p>
<p>And it is said (<i>qīl</i>) concerning the Exalted's statement: {And in what they spend (<i>anfaqūā</i>) of their wealth (<i>amwālihum</i>)}: in what they hand over (<i>sāqūā</i>)⁷⁰ [the women] in dowry and expenditure.</p> <p>Al-Shāfiʿī - God's mercy be upon him – interfered in the Exalted's statement: {Men are the maintainers of women...} [till the end of the] verse, on that marriage is not permitted except with a guardian, devoting (<i>ṣarafa</i>) the interpretation (<i>tā'wīl</i>) of the verse to them [i.e. guardians], and in {And in what they spend} requires (<i>yulzam</i>) guardians of expenditure, and [this] is not stated in it [i.e. the verse].</p> <p>And the following: So that the verse if in case it was about the guardian and total command over women it [i.e. the verse] would be proof (<i>ḥujja</i>) for them men; And He emitted that emitted right on them women in that men become guardians for women in contracts (<i>al-ʿUqūd</i>), and</p>	<p>وقيل في قوله - تعالى -: (وبما أنفقوا من أموالهم): بما ساقوا من المهر والنفقة.</p> <p>استدل الشافعي - رحمه الله - بقوله - تعالى -: (الرجال قوامون على النساء. . . الآية، على أن النكاح لا يجوز إلا بالولي، فصرف تأويل الآية إليهم، وفيها: (وبما أنفقوا) فيلزم الأولياء النفقة، وهو لا يقول به.</p> <p>وبعد: فإن الآية لو كانت في الأولياء فهو في كل أمر لهم إليهم حاجة؛ فيخرج ذلك مخرج الحق لهم في أن يتولوا لهم العقود كلها، ويقوموا في كفايتهم وكفالتهم، لا أنهم لو قمن بأنفسهن يبطل فعلهن؛ فمثله أمر النكاح.</p>

⁶⁷ This *sabab al-Nuzūl* is seemingly paraphrased by al-Māturīdī as most elements are present in similar *asbāb*, but not in these wordings or tenses. Some mention she was hit in the face, but none mention that there was also a trace left on her face. Compare to: Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:291-292. Jalāl al-Dīn al-Suyūfī, *al-Durr al-Manthūr fī al-Tafsīr bi-lMā'thūr* (Beirut: Dār al-Fikr, n.d.), 2:512-513. He also designated the tradition with *qīl*, which presumably indicates that he viewed it as coming from a weak source.

⁶⁸ See fn. 17 and 54 above. As women can not participate in warfare (*Jihād*), they can also not participate in warbooty (*faya* or *ghanā'im*).

⁶⁹ Here the tradition is cited as using “*aradnā* (we wanted)”, while the majority of versions of this *sabab* use “*aradtu* (I wanted)”. And none have the ending “...and God wanted something better than what we wanted.” See: Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:291. Al-Suyūfī, *Ibid*. This prophetic statement can be understood in a voluntarist fashion (i.e. God's will revealed through revelation supersedes human reasoned ethics as adhered to by the Ashʿarī theologians), or that the revealed good coincides with human reasoned good (i.e. natural law ethics) and must be discovered as God knows human interests better than anyone. Al-Māturīdī himself adhered to natural law ethics, whereby the ending of this *sabab* can be understood as being his own words. On Islamic voluntarist and natural law ethics, see: Emon, *Ibid*, 7ff. Arnold Yasin Mol, *Rational ethics and natural law in classical Islam: Examples from the Ḥanafī school*, 2016, accessed August 20, 2016, https://www.academia.edu/10939863/Rational_ethics_and_Natural_Law_in_classical_Islam_Examples_from_the_Ḥanafī_school.

⁷⁰ *Sāqūā* is a 3rd person perfect active masculine plural Form I verb from *sāqa*, and refers to drive, urge, carry along or transport something.

<p>maintaining in their sufficiency, not that the women if they undertake [a wedding contract] by themselves it becomes null (<i>yabṭul</i>) [because] they acted [by themselves]; So it is similar (<i>mithlahu</i>) to the command of marriage [in verse 2:232 that women should not be barred from marrying].</p> <p>And the people of interpretation relate the verse to the spouses, and someone who deliberated on the verse knows that it is in what the people of interpretation said (<i>qāl</i>) without (<i>duni</i>) holding the view of (<i>dhahaba ilāhi</i>) al-Shāfi'ī, and God knows best.⁷¹</p>	<p>وأهل التأويل يحملون الآية على الأزواج، ومن تدبر الآية علم أنها فيما قال أهل التأويل دون الذي ذهب إليه الشافعي، والله أعلم.</p>
<p>And the Mighty and Majestic stated: {So virtuous women (<i>al-ṣāliḥāt</i>) are those who are obedient (<i>qānitāt</i>)}.</p> <p>From Ibn ʿAbbās - may Allah be pleased with him – who said: <i>qānitāt</i> means: the obedient, and <i>al-Qānit</i>: He is the obedient.</p> <p>And possibly: They are obedient to God Exalted.</p> <p>And possibly: They are obedient to husbands.</p> <p>And possibly: <i>qānitāt</i> meaning: carrying out with fulfillment what is imposed (<i>farḍ</i>) on them women by God from His rights [in ethics and worship] and the rights from their husbands.</p> <p>And the Mighty and Majestic stated: {guardians of the absence (<i>ḥāfiẓāt li-lGhayb</i>)}.</p> <p>It is said (<i>qīl</i>): They guard what God entrusted them of His right, and they guard the absence in the absence of their husbands.</p> <p>And it is said (<i>qīl</i>): They guard themselves – in the absence of their husbands – their private parts (<i>furūjihunna</i>).</p> <p>And possibly: {guardians of the absence} meaning: For God in His commands and prohibitions, and the maintaining of His rights, and the obedient and guarding is the explanation (<i>tafsīr</i>) of being virtuous.</p> <p>And the Mighty and Majestic stated: {in what God has guarded} there is disagreement (<i>ikhtalaf</i>) in its recitation (<i>tilāwathu</i>) and</p>	<p>وقوله - عز وجل -: (فالصالحات قانتات). عن ابن عباس - رضي الله عنه - قال: (قانتات) يعني: مطيعات، والقانت: هو المطيع. ويحتمل: مطيعات لله تعالى: ويحتمل: مطيعات للأزواج. ويحتمل: (قانتات) أي: قائمات بأداء ما فرض الله عليهن من حقوقه وحقوق أزواجهن.</p> <p>وقوله - عز وجل -: (حافظات للغيب). قيل: حافظات لما استودعهن الله من حقه، وحافظات للغيب لغير أزواجهن. وقيل: حافظات لأنفسهن -لغيبية أزواجهن- في فروجهن.</p> <p>ويحتمل: (حافظات للغيب) أي: لله في أموره ونواهيها، والقيام بحقوقه، وقانتات وحافظات هو تفسير صالحات.</p> <p>وقوله - عز وجل -: (بما حفظ الله)</p>

⁷¹ See fn. 52 and 53 above. Al-Māturīdī rejects the idea that the verse proves the obligation for any form of guardianship, financially or otherwise, of men over women. His whole exegesis on {**Men are the maintainers of women because God has made one of them excel the other**} is in a sense a defense of the Hanafī position on guardianship, while almost all other Hanafī exegetes rather use this verse to state male ontological superiority. Even al-Māturīdī's student, Abū al-Layth al-Samarqandī (d. 986CE/375AH), whose exegesis typifies Hanafī *Fiqhi* exegesis does not apply al-Māturīdī's discourse (he has even written a commentary (*Sharḥ*) on al-Māturīdī's exegesis). See for comparison: Abū al-Layth al-Samarqandī, *Tafsīr al-Samarqandī aw Baḥr al-ʿUlūm* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-ʿIlmiyyah, 1993), 1:351 – 352.

<p>interpretation (<i>tā'wīlahu</i>); some bend (<i>ḥarrafa</i>) by linking {in what God has guarded} and its interpretation: {with the guarding of God}, [meaning] by His refuge (<i>lakannahu</i>) [which is understood by] to pronounce a declination⁷² (<i>li-suqūṭ</i>) of the letter of the final consonant (<i>al-Khafā</i>), and raising it (<i>rafa'ahu</i>)⁷³ [the final consonant] creates this interpretation: {in what God Exalted made them guard (<i>istahfazahunna</i>)}, and God knows best.</p>	<p>اختلف في تلاوته وتأويله؛ في حرف بعضهم بالنصب (بما حفظ الله) وتأويله: بحفظ الله، لكنه نصب لسقوط حرف الخفض، ومن رفعه جعل تأويله: بما استحفظهن الله تعالى، والله أعلم.</p>
<p>And the Mighty and Majestic stated: {As from those women you fear ill-conduct (<i>nushūzahun</i>)}. Some of the people of etiquette (<i>Ahl al-Adab</i>)⁷⁴ said (<i>qāl</i>): named the knowledge of fear (<i>al-ilm khawfā</i>); Because it is forced [upon someone by having certain] knowledge (<i>al-ilm</i>).⁷⁵ Another said (<i>qāl</i>) – and he was al-Farrā'⁷⁶ -: The fearful (<i>al-Khā'if</i>): The suspecting one (<i>al-Zānn</i>)⁷⁷; Because he hopes and fears. As for the foundation in that it is designated as knowledge of fear (<i>al-ilm khawfā</i>) [as opposed to being the speculation of fear]; [It is a means] in overcoming (<i>li-ghalba</i>) the intensity (<i>shidda</i>) of the fear; So to act with an action based on knowledge [while it is known] by something other than its facts (<i>ḥaqīqathu</i>) [i.e. speculation]; So it is known (<i>yuraf</i>) through reasoned diligence (<i>bi-litihād</i>), and through much reasoned opinion and speculation (<i>bi-akthar al-Rā'y wa al-Zānn</i>), and all such ways (<i>sabīl</i>) of knowledge of reasoned conclusion (<i>ma'rīfatihu al-ijtihād</i>) – so the speculation is [seemingly] overcome and to act on the strongest opinion with the action of certainty (<i>amal al-Yaqīn</i>) as if in the ruling of a judge (<i>ḥukm dayyān</i>) so nothing remains but [presumed] fact; But rather thinking as in the statement of the Exalted: {so you know them to be believers then do not send them back to the unbelievers (60:10)}, and we be</p>	<p>وقوله - عز وجل -: (واللاتي تخافون نشوزهن). قال بعض أهل الأدب: سمي العلم خوفاً؛ لأنه اضطر في العلم. وقال آخر - وهو الفراء -: الخائف: الظان؛ لأنه يرجو ويخاف. وأما الأصل في أنه سمي العلم خوفاً؛ لغلبة شدة الخوف؛ فيعمل عمل العلم بالشيء على غير حقيقته؛ لأنه يعرف بالاجتهاد، وبأكثر الرأي والظن، وهكذا كل ما كان سبيل معرفته الاجتهاد - فإن غالب الظن وأكبر الرأي يعمل عمل اليقين في الحكم ديان لم يكن هنالك حقيقة؛ ألا ترى إلى قوله تعالى -: (فإن علمتموهن مؤمنات فلا ترجعهن إلى الكفار)، وألزمنا العمل بظاهر علمنا وإن لم نصل إلى حقيقة إيمانهن؛ فعلى ذلك إذا علم منها النشوز علم أكثر الظن وأغلبه يعمل عمل الذي ذكر في الآية من العظة وغيرها؛ لأن قوله - تعالى -: (تخافون نشوزهن) ليس على وجود النشوز منها للحال حقيقة؛ ولكن على غالب الظن؛ لأنها إذا كانت ناشزة كيف يعظها؛ وكيف يهجرها ويضربها؛ فدل أنه على غالب العلم؛ ألا ترى أنه من أكره على أن ينطق بكلام الكفر بقتل أو ضرب يخاف منه التلف - كان في حل وسعة أن ينطق به بعد أن يكون قلبه مطمئناً بالإيمان، وذلك إنما يعلم علم غالب الظن، وأكبر الرأي لا يعلم علم حقيقة، ثم أبيض له أن يعمل عمل حقيقة العلم؛</p>

⁷² Meaning the word *Allah* is in the genitive case (i.e. *Allahī*), which makes Him the doer of the guarding.

⁷³ Meaning the word *Allah* is in the accusative case (i.e. *Allaha*), which makes Him the one who lets others guard.

⁷⁴ The people of etiquette (*Ahl al-Adab*) refers to those scholars who focus on the *Fiqh* of behaviour, good manners, education, and etiquette. A famous example of a work on *adab* is written by al-Māturīdī's student al-Samarqandī: *Tanbīh al-Ghāfilīn* (admonition of the Neglectful).

⁷⁵ On fear based on knowledge, see also fn. 31 above.

⁷⁶ Referring to another early scholar of linguistics, Yaḥya ibn Ziyād al-Farrā' (d. 823CE/207AH), and his version of *Ma'ānī al-Qur'ān*. For the referred statement, see: Yaḥya ibn Ziyād al-Farrā', *Ma'ānī al-Qur'ān* (Beirut: 'Ālam al-Kutub, 1983), 1:265.

⁷⁷ On fear based on speculation, see also fn. 32 above.

required to act on the evident (*bi-zāhir*) that we know off and that we do not relate it (*lam naṣil*) to their actual faith (*ḥaqīqat īmānahunna*); And so that when knowledge of her ill-conduct is known through much speculation and this overcomes him he [thinks] can act by what is mentioned in the verse of admonition and other such things; Because the Exalted said {**you fear ill-conduct**} without that the ill-conduct needs to exist as a factual condition; So [he thinks he can act] on the dominance of speculation [alone]; But when she is [truly] acting with ill-conduct (*nāshiza*) how do you admonish, or abandon, or hit her? So this proves that [this requires] the predominance of certain knowledge (*ghālib al-‘ilm*)⁷⁸; Or does he think that he can force [her] by uttering (*yanṭuq*) with words of apostasy (*bi-kalām al-Kufr*), with murder (*bi-qatl*) or hitting, fearing from him harm (*al-Talaḥ*)⁷⁹ – [And when] he is in a condition to be capable to speak with it [i.e. admonishment] after his heart is at ease (*muṭma'inā*) with faith, and on the contrary knows that only certain knowledge overcomes speculation, and that even the strongest opinion does not inform on real facts, then it is permitted for him that he acts on the actual knowledge;

And so also is the first [i.e. admonishment] – and God knows best – God forbid - the Mighty and Majestic – that the wife rebels (*‘iṣyān*) against her husband, and he commands her to obey by herself, as his command is that he improves

فكذلك الأول - والله أعلم - نهى الله - عز وجل - المرأة عن عصيان زوجها، وأمرها بطاعته في نفسها، كما أمره أن يحسن عشرتها، وهذا هو - والله أعلم - هو الحق الذي ذكره الله - تعالى - في سورة البقرة مجملا بقوله - تعالى -: (ولهن مثل الذي عليهن بالمعروف)، وفسر الحق عليهن في هذه السورة وهو أن تطيعه في نفسها، وتحفظ غيبته؛ ألا ترى أنه قال - تعالى -: (فإن أطعنكم فلا تبغوا عليهن سبيلا).

⁷⁸ Here al-Māturīdī rejects the opinion that a man can admonish, leave and hit his wife purely because he speculates and worries she is cheating on him. Although the verse seemingly says one only needs to fear the ill-conduct without its factual presence, al-Māturīdī wonders what to do when she really cheats on him. This proves to him that one can only admonish, leave and hit her based on real knowledge the cheating has occurred. Otherwise one rules like a judge, but without facts of the crime, and in Islamic law it is forbidden to apply punishments when there is doubt (*shubha*). The accumulation of opinions and speculations can lead to a reasoned conclusion (*ijtihād*) that the wife is cheating on him, but judgement (*ḥukm*) is based on facts and not on reasoned conclusions. Wrongful accusations or insufficient evidence of adultery is termed *Qadhf* and can lead to eighty lashes for the accuser in court, based on verses 24:4-10. Although al-Māturīdī does not explain the term *nushūz*, it is clear he understands it here as referring to sexual misconduct and adultery in the way as stated above at fn. 31. On the position of doubt in Islamic law, see: Intisar A. Rabb, *Doubt in Islamic law: A history of legal maxims, interpretation, and Islamic criminal law* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2014), 48-68, 135–322. On *Qadhf*, see: Al-Zuhaylī, *al-Fiqh al-Islamiyyu*, 7:5396-5421.

⁷⁹ Al-Māturīdī here uses a hyperbole to mockingly answer his previous question: if admonishment, leaving and hitting is already allowed with speculation of ill-conduct, what is allowed with actual ill-conduct? Saying she is an apostate, or killing her, or hitting her so she comes to fear him? It is therefore clear to al-Māturīdī that speculation is not the condition which triggers admonishment, abandonment and hitting her.

<p>(<i>yuḥassana</i>) their intimacy (<i>‘ishratahā</i>)⁸⁰, and this is – and God knows best – is the right which God the Exalted mentioned – in sūrah al-Baqarah summarized in the Exalted’s statement: {and for them are similar [rights] which are upon them in accordance with common goodness (2:228)}⁸¹, and it explains (<i>fasara</i>) the right which is upon them women in this sūrah and is that she obeys him by herself, and she guards his unseen⁸²; [Therefore] desist thinking [bad about her] as the Exalted said {If they, then, obey you (<i>aṭa ‘nakum</i>), you shall seek no other way (<i>sabīlān</i>) against them}.</p> <p>And it is narrated from the Messenger of God (<i>ṣaws</i>) that he said: “The right of the husband over his wife is that he calls her and she hunches (<i>qatab</i>)⁸³ over to obey him.”</p>	<p>وروي عن رسول الله - صلى الله عليه وسلم - أنه قال: " حق الزوج على امرأته إن دعاها وهي على قتب أن تطيعه ".</p>
<p>And the Mighty and Majestic said: {admonish them} And Ibn ‘Abbās - may God be pleased with him – said: Admonish them with the book of God [i.e. the Qur’ān]⁸⁴ {so that they obey you} meaning they return to bed and are obedient, and otherwise abandon them and the separation (<i>al-Hajr</i>) is not to have intercourse with her (<i>yujāmi‘hā</i>), and do not have sexual intercourse with her on the bed, and refrain from her (<i>yuwalīhā</i>)⁸⁵ in the afternoon (<i>al-Zuhr</i>)⁸⁶, so if she will accept you and only by the authority of God has He authorized you to hit but hit without violence (<i>ghayri mubarriḥ</i>), and do not fracture her bones (<i>‘azmā</i>), so if she will accept you however the dissolution [of the marriage] is that</p>	<p>وقوله - عز وجل - : (فعظوهن) عن ابن عباس - رضي الله عنه - قال: عظوهن بكتاب الله (فإن أظعنكم) أي رجعن إلى الفراش والطاعة، وإلا فاهجروهن، والهجران ألا يجامعها، ولا يضاجعها على فراشه، ويوليها الظهر، فإن قبلت وإلا فقد أذن الله لك أن تضربها ضربا غير مبرح، ولا تكسر لها عظاما، فإن قبلت وإلا فقد حل لك منها الفداء.</p>

⁸⁰ Here al-Māturīdī directly links obeying the husband in fulfilling his sexual needs (i.e. the command) in that he will also take care of her sexual needs, which would take away her need to reject him or cheat on him.

⁸¹ This verse is generally understood to refer to general rights and obligations of husband and wife, but it is also understood to specifically mean equivalence in rights to sexual intimacy. See: Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 4:531.

⁸² Meaning she takes care of his intimate needs, and through that preserve and protect them against sin.

⁸³ *Qatab* means to hunch or bend over, classical dictionaries explain it as “the camel which hunches over so he can be mounted.” Seemingly al-Māturīdī cites this prophetic tradition as an expansion of linking spousal obedience to sexual relations. See: Al-Māturīdī, *Tā’wīlāt al-Qur’ān*, 3:204, fn. 7.

⁸⁴ Al-Ṭabarī, *Ibid*, 8:300.

⁸⁵ The verb *yuwalīhā* is a 3rd person singular form I passive imperfect verb from *walā*, which can mean to take charge or possession over something, but also has the meaning of turning away and refrain from it, I have applied to latter meaning due to the expected continuation of the act of separation.

⁸⁶ In the Middle East it was (and largely still is) the custom to retreat to the houses and beds during the hottest time of the day, i.e. noon. This is also referred to in verse 24:58 when people put off their clothing during noon.

<p>you receive from her a ransom (<i>al-Fidā'</i>) [i.e. payment for <i>Khul'</i>].⁸⁷</p> <p>And it is possible the Exalted states {admonish them}: Say to her: You should be from the virtuous and from the obedient and from the guarding, and you are not from those who are gentle (<i>al-Rifq</i>) and compliant (<i>al-Līn</i>); so she leaves (<i>tarakat</i>) that [bad behaviour behind] and [if not then] abandon her, and abandonment (<i>al-Hijr</i>) has two possible aspects: Potential intimidation of separation (<i>al-i'tizāl</i>) from her [i.e. divorce], leaving the bed and sexual intercourse.</p>	<p>ويحتمل قوله - تعالى - : (فعضوهن): يقول لها: كوني من الصالحات، ومن القانتات، ومن الحافظات، ولا تكوني من كذا، على الرفق واللين؛ فإن هي تركت ذلك وإلا فاهجرها، والهجران يحتمل وجهين: يحتمل التخويف على الاعتزال منها، وترك المضاجعة والجماع.</p>
<p>And possibly: That you abandon her and not have intercourse with her, while not [yourself] being fearful from leaving [intercourse]; if she leaves [any wish to have intercourse] then hit her at [that moment] and the hitting is as we mentioned without violence, and without disgracing her⁸⁸, and God knows best.</p> <p>On the sequence [of the admonishments]: first he admonishes her through what we mentioned from of gentleness and compliancy causing her to obey him and leave [the ill-conduct], then when she does not obey him scare her through the abandoning; So it will cause her to reverse [her ways] (<i>qalabahā</i>) as it is not likely to abandon [any sexual contact] and leave the bed [at the same time]; So [hopefully] she will obey him; as she will desire it and on that moment abandon her, and do not have sexual relations with her and do not bed her; So [hopefully] she will obey him and [only when she still continues the ill-conduct] hit her; So [hopefully] she will obey him and [if she still continues with her ill-conduct] then he must take it up to the judge (<i>al-Hākim</i>)⁸⁹, and this is what he is obligated to do in the commanding towards the common good and forbidding the wrong (<i>al-Amr bi-lMa'rūf wa al-Nahī 'an al-Munkar</i>)⁹⁰: He admonishes her to</p>	<p>ويحتمل: أن يهجرها ولا يجامعها، لا على التخويف من ترك ذلك؛ فإن هي تركت ذلك وإلا ضربها عند ذلك الضرب الذي ذكرنا غير مبرح، ولا شائن، والله أعلم.</p> <p>على الترتيب: يعظها أولاً بما ذكرنا من الرفق بها واللين لعلها تطيعه وتترك ذلك، ثم إذا لم تطعه خوفها بالهجران؛ ففعل قلبها لا يحتمل الهجران وترك المضاجعة؛ فتطيعه؛ فإن هي أبت ذلك حينئذ هجرها، ولم يجامعها ولا يضاجعها؛ فإن هي أطاعته وإلا عند ذلك ضربها؛ فإن هي أطاعته وإلا فعند ذلك يرفعان إلى الحاكم، وهذا يجب في الأمر بالمعروف والنهي عن المنكر: يعظه على الرفق واللين أولاً، ولا يغلظه في القول؛ فإن هو قبل ذلك وإلا عند ذلك غلظ القول به؛ فإن قبل ذلك وإلا بسط يده فيه على ما أمر الله - سبحانه وتعالى - الأزواج أن تعامل النساء من العظة، ثم الهجران، ثم الضرب، ثم الرفع إلى الحكيم.</p>

⁸⁷ This tradition understands the three admonishments as a sequence, see fn. 39 above. The ransom refers to payment a wife makes to her husband so she can get divorced, see fn. 23 above.

⁸⁸ See fn. 43 above.

⁸⁹ The *Hākim* can refer to a judge or someone with the authority of a judge such as a governor or ruler, or when those are not available, a local acknowledged arbiter. This person must appoint arbiters from among each family as commanded in verse 4:35. See: Spectorsky, *Ibid*, 174-176.

⁹⁰ This refers to the individual and public duty of ethical advising and correcting Muslims and non-Muslims, as commanded in verse 3:110/114, and is generally termed *Hisba*. On classical notions of *Hisba*, see: Michael A. Cook, *Commanding Right and Forbidding Wrong in Islamic Thought* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2001), 13-31, 32ff.

<p>be gentle and compliant or not, and he should not be coarse (<i>yughlīz</i>) in his speech; As it was prior before [the ill-conduct] and [if she still continues the ill-conduct] then use coarse speech; So it will be as before [the ill-conduct] and if not then he should extend his hand (<i>basāṭa yaddahu</i>) as God commanded – He be praised and exalted – the husbands that he deals with women through admonishment, then abandonment, then hitting, then take it up to two arbiters [as commanded in verse 4:35].</p>	
<p>And it is related in a report from the Messenger of God (<i>ṣaws</i>) saying: “Do not strike (<i>lā taḍribūā</i>) the handmaidens (<i>imā'</i>) of God”⁹¹, therefore that people leave out [the act of] beating women⁹², then ʿUmar arrived -may God be pleased with him-and he said: “By God has He regulated (<i>dabbara</i>)⁹³ the women, O Messenger of God?”; Then He commanded to beat them [by revealing this verse]⁹⁴, he said⁹⁵: “Then many women surrounded the family of Muḥammad to complain about their husbands”, after it I accompanied⁹⁶ the Messenger of God</p>	<p>وروي في الخبر عن رسول الله - صلى الله عليه وسلم - قال: " لا تضربوا إماء الله "؛ فترك الناس ضربهن، فجاء عمر - رضي الله عنه - فقال: والله لقد دبر النساء يا رسول الله؛ فأمر بضربهن، قال: فأطاف بال محمد النساء كثيرا يشتكين أزواجهن، فلما أصبح رسول الله - صلى الله عليه وسلم - قال: " لقد أطاف الليلة بال محمد سبعون امرأة يشتكين الضرب، والله ما تجدون أولئك خياركم "،</p>

⁹¹ This part is mentioned, all in the same wording, by many famous Hadīth collections. See: Abū Dāwud al-Sajistānī, *Sunan Abū Dāwud* (Beirut: al-Maktabat al-ʿAṣriya, n.d.), 2:245, Ḥadīth 2146. Abū Bakr al-Bayhaqī, *al-Sunan al-Kubrā* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-ʿIlmiyyah, 2003), 7:496-498, Ḥadīth 14775/14781. Ibn Ḥibān, *Ṣaḥīḥ Ibn Ḥibān* (Beirut: Muʿassasat al-Risāla, 1988), 9:499. Abū al-Qāsim al-Ṭabarānī, *al-Muʿjam al-Kabīr li-lṬabarānī* (Cairo: Maktabat Ibn Taymiyyah, 1994), 1:27, Ḥadīth 784/785/786. Abū ʿAbd Allah al-Ḥākim al-Naysābūrī, *al-Mustadarak ʿalā al-Ṣaḥīḥayn* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-ʿIlmiyyah, 1990), 2:205, Ḥadīth 2765/2774. Muḥammad al-Shawkānī, *Nayl al-ʿAwṭār* (Egypt: Dār al-Ḥadīth, 1993), 6:251. Mullā ʿAlī al-Qārī, *Mirqāt al-Mafātīḥ Sharḥ Mishkāṭ al-Maṣābīḥ* (Beirut: Dār al-Fikr, 2002), 5:2127.

⁹² This sentence is only in al-Ṭabarānī 786, but Ibn Ḥibān and al-Bayhaqī narrate a similar sentence after the the command to strike was given: “...The Prophet (*ṣaws*) said: ‘so strike’ so people struck their wives till the evening...”. Ibn Ḥibān. Al-Bayhaqī 14775. In both versions the sentences are descriptions of the events inserted by the narrator.

⁹³ The manuscripts of al-Māturīdī’s exegesis all have *dabbara* (to manage, organize, regulate, arrange. 3rd person masculine singular perfect tense), but this Ḥadīth, in all the versions in the mentioned collections, is known only with the verb *dha’ir* (to rebel, be emboldened) providing the meaning: “...the women have rebelled O Messenger of God”. Also all versions have “...*dha’ir al-Nisā’ ʿalā azwājihunna* (the women rebel against their husbands), and al-Māturīdī’s version lacks *ʿalā azwājihunna*. The majority of traditions use *dha’ir* in combination with “*wa sā’at akhlāqunna* (and became bad in their character)”, which also lacks here. So it is possible (although unlikely) the manuscripts are correct in that al-Māturīdī related this Ḥadīth with *dabbara*, whereby it is a *sabab al-Nuzūl* tradition as I have maintained here (al-Shawkānī also classifies it as such). See also the upheld correction in the Turkish edition: Al-Māturīdī, *Tā’wīlāt al-Qur’ān*, 3:206, fn. 1.

⁹⁴ Several versions clearly state the Prophet gave the permission. Others leave it more open whereby it is possible they refer to permission granted by God through revelation. If we retain the wording as stated here, whereby ʿUmar directly asks about God’s position, it is possible the permission is given by the revelation of verse 4:34. The difference in tone also matters as here it uses *amr*, command, while the other versions mostly use *rakḥḥaṣa*, permitted, which is generally used as allowing something normally forbidden or disliked out of necessity or special favor.

⁹⁵ It is unclear who the speaker here is due to the 3rd person tense, but I assume it is the prophetic companion Iyās b. ʿAbd Allah b. Abū Dhubāb who is the narrator of this Ḥadīth and who is paraphrased here.

⁹⁶ Again I assume it is the prophetic companion Abū Dhubāb but now in the first person tense.

<p>(<i>ṣaws</i>) [and] he said: “Tonight seventy⁹⁷ women surrounded the family of Muḥammad to complain about the beating (<i>al-Ḍarb</i>)⁹⁸, and by God what is given to you (<i>tujdūna</i>)⁹⁹ [of husbands] are not (<i>mā</i>)¹⁰⁰ the best among you (<i>khayārakum</i>).”¹⁰¹</p> <p>And he [the Prophet] said: “The best of you (<i>khayrakum</i>) is best for his family, and I'm the best of you for my family,”¹⁰² and he said: “The best (<i>aḥsan</i>) believers in faith are best in character (<i>khulqā</i>) and kind with his family.”¹⁰³</p> <p>It is said (<i>qāl</i>): A word of admonishment softens (<i>yulayyin</i>) the cruelest hearts, and desires a timid nature (<i>al-Ṭabā'ic al-Nāfira</i>); So they are to be reminded of the consequences (<i>awāqib</i>) of [these] matters (<i>umūr</i>), and the starting points of these situations (<i>mabādī' al-Aḥwāl</i>), and God knows best.</p> <p>And on [these matters] does her husband admonish her with what he reminds her of the blessings of the Lord (<i>na'im al-Rabb</i>) – Majestic in His Majesty – and what He creates of the rights on her, and what He promises and has promised.</p>	<p>وقال: " خيركم خيركم لأهله، وأنا خيركم لأهلي " وقال: " أحسن المؤمنين إيماناً أحسنهم خلقاً وأطفهم بأهله ".</p> <p>قال: والموعظة كلام يلين القلوب القاسية، ويرغب الطباع النافرة؛ فيكون ذلك تذكير عواقب الأمور ومبادئ الأحوال، والله أعلم.</p> <p>وعلى ذلك يعظها زوجها بأن يذكرها نعم الرب - جل جلاله - وما جعل من الحق عليها، وما وعد في ذلك وأوعد.</p>
<p>So in these verses is an interfered [meaning] (<i>dalāla</i>) which requires reasoned diligence (<i>al-ijtihād</i>) and responsibility (<i>taklīf</i>) for what is not communicated of knowledge (<i>ma'rifat</i>) to the responsible person (<i>al-Mukallaf</i>) [so to understand this interference and can only be deduced] except with deep reflection (<i>al-Tadabbur</i>) and exposition (<i>al-ʿArḍ</i>) of the customs or the rational causes (<i>al-Asbāb al-Maʿqūla</i>) in bringing about causes for welfare interests (<i>asbābā li-lMaṣlaḥa</i>)¹⁰⁴; And a means</p>	<p>ففي هذه الآيات دلالة لزوم الاجتهاد وتكليف ما لا يوصل إلى معرفة المكلف به إلا بالتدبر والعرض على الأمور المعتادة أو الأسباب المعقولة في جعلها أسباباً للمصلحة، وسبباً للوقوف على ما في أصول تلك النوازل من الحكمة، ولا قوة إلا بالله.</p>

⁹⁷ Using *sabaʿūn* (seventy; al-Hākim 2774, al-Bayhaqī 14775), majority uses *kathīr* (many; Abū Dāwud, al-Hākim 2765). Generally, *sabaʿūn* is seen as a synonym for *kathīr*.

⁹⁸ Al-Ṭabarānī 784. Is lacking in all other versions.

⁹⁹ Al-Bayhaqī 14775/14781. *Tujdūna* is a 2nd person Form I imperfect passive tense verb from *judā*, meaning to give or bestow a present.

¹⁰⁰ Uses *mā* (al-Ṭabarānī 786) instead of *laysa* (Abū Dāwud 2146, al-Hākim 2765/2774), or *lā* (al-Ṭabarānī 7784/85, al-Bayhaqī 14775).

¹⁰¹ From the above assessment it is clear that al-Māturīdī related a version which has been discarded or is unknown to the major collections, or he has used a selection from the several known versions and partially paraphrased it as it contains many elements not extant in the other versions.

¹⁰² Al-Qārī, *Ibid*, 5:2125.

¹⁰³ Known with *akmāl* (perfect) instead of *aḥsan*. Al-Qārī, *Ibid*, 5:2128, 8:3185.

¹⁰⁴ Meaning the one charged with the responsibility for attaining the best reasoned conclusion (*ijtihād*), i.e. the *Mujtahid*, must through deep reflection and exposition of customs and logical causes of marital harmony

<p>for the suspending [of rights] (<i>li-lWuqūf</i>)¹⁰⁵ in accordance with the principles (<i>uṣūl</i>)¹⁰⁶ [in pursuit of general welfare whereby] the events (<i>al-Nawāzil</i>) [are to be understood as] belonging to the [divine] wisdom (<i>al-Ḥikma</i>)¹⁰⁷, and there is no power except through God.¹⁰⁸ Then He makes disciplining women [as a means] for the spouses, and not for the rulers (<i>al-'imma</i>); because the punishment (<i>'aqūba</i>) of the rulers would consist of hitting [by whip or cane] or confinement (<i>ḥabs</i>)¹⁰⁹ and the disliked (<i>al-Makrūh</i>) [in punishment] is not attached to the command of [spousal] disciplining as it [the spousal disciplining] is accompanied with what belongs to the veil (<i>al-Sitr</i>) [of privacy], and it is predominance (<i>al-Ghālib</i>) [of certain knowledge of ill-conduct] which do not provide¹¹⁰</p>	<p>ثم جعل تأديبهن إلى الأزواج، لا إلى الأئمة؛ إذ عقوبة الأئمة تكون بالضرب أو الحبس وما يلحقها من المكروه فيما له أمر بالتأديب مع ما في ذلك من الستر، ويكون الغالب منه ما لا يجد لسبيل الإظهار عند الحاكم، ويكون في أوقات تضيق عن احتمال ذلك، ويكون ذلك أصلاً لتأديب كل كافل أحد من الأيتام والصغار، وغير ذلك، والله أعلم.</p>
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and discord bring about the best interpretation and application of this verse in pursuit of bringing about general welfare (*maṣlaḥa*).

¹⁰⁵ The suspending of his and her rights in hitting or sexual intercourse.

¹⁰⁶ The principles refer to the principles of interpretation (as in *uṣūl al-Fiqh* or *uṣūl al-Tafsīr*), but also to the principle foundational concepts that pertain to marital situations, which he discusses below.

¹⁰⁷ The concept of divine wisdom is central to al-Māturīdī's theology: "[I]ndicators of wisdom are in fact found everywhere in the world. God did not hide His decisions, but actually imparted them in a form understandable to all humans. This is evident on numerous levels: in the harmonious direction (*tabḥīr*) of the creation; in the rationality of ethical norms; and even in the way in which God creates harmful life forms and substances (*al-ḥayyāt wa-l-jawāhir al-dārra*) for specific reasons. In all of these cases, divine wisdom is at work, and it manifests itself systematically so that human beings can perceive the clues of its existence. [...] [T]he principle of divine wisdom [...] is reflected in all things, [...] divine wisdom (*ḥikma*) expresses itself in two ways (*ṭarīqān*). One is the way of grace (*faḍl*), and the other is the way of justice (*'adl*). Al-Māturīdī considers God's goodness to be immeasurable. It has no end (*nihāya*). [...] God is wise because He "puts everything in its (proper) place". Ulrich, *Ibid*, 298-299.

¹⁰⁸ The sentence "there is no power except through God" is a term of piety referring to that the interpreter is ontologically dependent on God: "[A]s said by al-Māturīdī, every word in the Qur'an has many probable meanings whose truth are tentative and uncertain because no one knows the truest meaning of the Quranic verses, except Allah, the Omniscient. Therefore, al-Māturīdī often closes his quotations with the following statements: *wa bi Allāh al-tawfīq* (and the assistance is from Allah), *wa Allāh musta'ān* (and Allah is the only One whose help is sought), *wa lā quwwah illā bi Allāh* (and there is no power, except from Allah), *wa Allāh a'lam* (and Allah is the Omniscient), *wa Allāh a'lam bi mā arād* (and Allah is the Omniscient on its meaning), *wa bi Allāh al-ma'ūah wa al-'iṣmah* (and both the assistance and protection are from Allah), *wa Allāh al-muwaffīq* (and Allah is the helper) and *wa bi Allāh al-'iṣmah* (and the protection is from Allah)." Rofiq, *Ibid*, 329.

¹⁰⁹ Here al-Māturīdī makes a clear distinction between public governance and private family governance. To al-Māturīdī the disciplinary admonitions are meant to solve these matters (i.e. her sexual misconduct) by families themselves so they can avoid the judge. Although the majority of exegetes agree on this, the emphasis laid here is a typical Ḥanafī principle. See: Christian Lange, *Justice, punishment and the medieval Muslim imagination* (Cambridge, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2008), 214, 222. There is also agreement on that the hitting can not be done with a whip or cane. See: Al-Jaṣṣāṣ, *Ibid*, 2:237 – 238. And fn. 43 above. Interestingly, modern scholars as Ṭahir Ibn 'Ashūr (d. 1972CE) disagree on this matter as he fears common people apply it wrongfully. Al-Māturīdī on the other hand fears that governance punishments go to far. See: Ṭahir Ibn 'Ashūr, *Tafsīr al-Taḥrīr wa al-Tanwīr* (Tunis: Dār Sahnun lil-Nushr wa-lTawziy 'a, z.d.), 5:37 – 44.

¹¹⁰ The verb *yajd* is a 3rd person singular masculine imperfect tense from from *judā*, meaning to give or bestow a present, as is also used in the Ḥadīth above at fn. 99.

<p>[evidence] of the way of evident as [is required] with the judge, and in that moment (<i>awqāt</i>) restricts (<i>taḍīq</i>)¹¹¹ what is possible [in disciplining], and this makes the principle (<i>aṣlān</i>) for disciplining for all supporting protectors (<i>kulli kāfil</i>)¹¹² [like] someone from the orphans and [who commits] minor sins (<i>al-Ṣaghā'ir</i>)¹¹³, and God knows best.</p>	
<p>And the principle (<i>al-Aṣl</i>): Is that God the Exalted said: {And among His Signs is this, that He created (<i>khalāqa</i>) for you mates from among yourselves, that you may dwell in tranquility with them, and He has made (<i>ja'ala</i>)¹¹⁴ love (<i>mawadda</i>) and mercy (<i>raḥma</i>) between you (30:21)}, therefore making the disciplining from the aspect which in it preserves what is made (<i>al-Maj'ūla</i>) for us¹¹⁵, and is a protective custody (<i>ri'āya</i>)¹¹⁶ what is made between them from love and mercy, and heavy disputes (<i>al-Munāz'āt</i>)¹¹⁷ and lawsuits (<i>al-Khuṣūmāt</i>)¹¹⁸ are brought to the judge who discontinues (<i>yuqaṭṭ'</i>)¹¹⁹ that [i.e. the marriage]; Therefore it [the relationship made with love and mercy] is made for them [spouses] to determine (<i>qadara</i>) not to discontinue (<i>lā yaqaṭ'</i>) to go together with (<i>mithlahu min</i>) the disciplining [with] the meaning [of being part of what is also] made between them [of love and mercy]; And therefore no authority is given for violent hitting. And no authority is given except with [an intent of a] discontinuation (<i>inqaṭā'</i>)¹²⁰ of the stratagem</p>	<p>والأصل: أن الله - تعالى - قال: (ومن آياته أن خلق لكم من أنفسكم أزواجا لتسكنوا إليها وجعل بينكم مودة ورحمة)، فجعل التأديب من الوجه الذي فيه حفظ المَجْعُول لنا - آية، ورعاية ما جعل بينهم من المودة والرحمة، والمنازعات والخصومات إلى الحكام يقطع تلك؛ فجعل لهم من ذلك قدر ما لا يقطع مثله من التأديب المعنى المَجْعُول بينهم؛ ولذلك لم تأذن بالضرب المبرح، ولا أذن إلا عند انقطاع الحيل التي جعلت للألفة والمحبة، على أن في خفيف ذلك إظهار الإشفاق على ما اعترض من خوف انقطاع المودة والرحمة، وإبداء العتاب الذي هو آية النصح والرحمة؛ إذ ذلك مما يخاف في ترك ذلك تمام ما قد افتتح من السر والشفقة، والله أعلم.</p>

¹¹¹ The verb *taḍīq* is a form I imperfect active 3rd person of *ḍāq*, which means something narrow, tightened or restricted.

¹¹² *Kāfil* is a singular noun from *kafala*, meaning a person charged with the responsibility to protect and sustain others.

¹¹³ In Islamic theology, sins are classified in minor (*ṣaghā'ir*) and major (*kabā'ir*), whereby the former can be forgiven and compensated by worship and common acts of goodness (verses 4:31, 42:37, and 53:32), while the latter are completely dependent on God's will and mercy and can make a believer be put into hell temporarily. See: Aḥmad Fariḍ al-Mazidi, Ed., *Shuruḥ wa Ḥawashi al-'Aqā'id al-Nasafiyya li-Ahl al-Sunna wa-l-Jama'ā al-Asha'ira wa-l-Māturīdiyya* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyyah, 2013), 4:423 – 433.

¹¹⁴ The mates are ontologically and materially created, *khalāqa*, while love and mercy is made, *ja'ala*, for that which is created. Al-Māturīdī uses variants of *ja'ala* in his explanation here to show he is referring to the love and mercy.

¹¹⁵ Meaning that disciplining should preserve and not destroy relationships with love and mercy.

¹¹⁶ The verbal noun *ri'āya* is from *r'ā* and refers to protection and care of something.

¹¹⁷ *Al-Muāz'āt* is a female plural noun from *naz'a*, and refers to a heavy conflict, struggle or dispute.

¹¹⁸ *Al-Khuṣūmāt* is a female plural noun from *khaṣama* and refers to a quarrel or lawsuit between adversaries.

¹¹⁹ *Yuqaṭṭ'* from *qaṭ'*, meaning to cut or separate. The verb *yuqaṭṭ'* is in the imperfect tense, while grammatically the perfect tense (*taqaṭṭ'*) is more suitable, as also the editors of the Dār Mīzān edition have argued: Al-Māturīdī, *Tā'wīlāt al-Qur'ān*, 3:207 fn. 11.

¹²⁰ *Inqaṭā'* is a form VII verbal noun from *qaṭ'*.

<p>(<i>al-Ḥiyal</i>)¹²¹ [i.e. the disciplining] which makes affection (<i>li-Ulfa</i>)¹²² and love (<i>maḥabba</i>)¹²³, by [applying] light (<i>khafīfa</i>) [hitting] which is a manifestation of compassionate anxiety (<i>al-ishfāq</i>)¹²⁴ on what he objects to (<i>ʿitarāḍa</i>)¹²⁵ from fear (<i>kawf</i>) to discontinue the love and mercy, and begins the reprimand (<i>al- iʿtāb</i>) which is a verse of advice and mercy (<i>ayat al-Naṣḥ wa al-Raḥma</i>); Because that [person is one who] is afraid in leaving that perfection (<i>tamām</i>) [i.e. a loving marriage] introduces (<i>iftataḥ</i>)¹²⁶ a man who treats with goodness, affection and gentleness (<i>al-Sarr</i>)¹²⁷ and tenderness (<i>al-Shifaqa</i>), and God knows best.¹²⁸</p>	
<p>And it is said (<i>qīl</i>) concerning the Exalted's statement: {And in what they spend (<i>anfaqū</i>) of their wealth (<i>amwālithum</i>)}: in what they</p>	<p>وقيل في قوله - تعالى -: (وبما أنفقوا من أموالهم): بما ساقوا من المهر والنفقة.</p>

¹²¹ The plural noun *al-Ḥiyal* from *ḥīla* from the verb *ḥawala* refers to a maneuver, stratagem, or legal device which tries to accomplish a certain end. It is a term which specifically is used for analogical devices first developed by Ḥanafī Fiqh: “The legal devices, which form an integral part of Islamic law as applied in practice, can be described as the use of legal means for extra-legal ends, ends that could not, whether they themselves were legal or illegal, be achieved directly with the means provided by the *sharīʿa*. They enabled persons who would otherwise have had no choice but to act against the provisions of the sacred Law, to arrive at the desired result while actually conforming to the letter of the law.” *Encyclopaedia of Islam, Second Edition* (2012), s.v “*Ḥiyal*” by J. Schacht, edited by P. Bearman e.a., accessed August 15, 2016, http://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/encyclopaedia-of-islam-2/hiyal-SIM_2913. It is clear al-Māturīdī treats the disciplining allowed by 4:34 to be like a *Ḥiyal* as it is a way to correct sexual misconduct outside the order of law, whereby the hitting is only allowed to end the discord and ill-conduct, not to continue it.

¹²² The noun *Ulfa* from *alifa* refers to intimacy, friendship, love, affection, harmony and union.

¹²³ The verbal noun *maḥabba* from *ḥabba* refers to love, like or want something, and is a synonym of *mawadda* from *wadda* as used in verse 30:21.

¹²⁴ The form IV verbal noun *ishfāq* from *shafīqa* and refers to having pity, sympathy, compassion and tenderness, but also to be beware, anxious, worried and cautious.

¹²⁵ The verb *ʿitarāḍa* is a form VIII 3rd person singular masculine perfect active verb from *ʿarāḍa* which refers to opposing, objecting, resisting something. Meaning the spouse is anxious and objects to using hitting as a means as it can discontinue the love and mercy between the couple.

¹²⁶ The verb *iftataḥ* is a form VIII 3rd person singular masculine perfect active verb of *fataḥa*.

¹²⁷ The manuscript has *al-Yusr* (ease or facility), which is corrected here by Dār al-Kutub into *al-Sarr* (a man who treats with goodness and affection and gentleness), and by Dār al-Mīzān into *al-Sharr* (evil, malice, harm, injury). The Dār al-Kutub correction is possible and fits the context perfectly, while the Dār al-Mīzān correction is illogical, but I believe the original *al-Yusr* also fits here. Al-Māturīdī, *Tāʾwīlāt al-Qurʾān*, 3:207, fn. 19. On *Sarr*, see: Lane, *Ibid*, 1:1338.

¹²⁸ Again it can be stated that this exegesis is rare among classical and modern exegetes, as it makes love and mercy as the determining condition for marriage and therefore also if and how any chastisement is performed. If the disciplining does not achieve to preserve love and mercy, one must restrain from it, as if the marriage has already lost these elements then one should just go to a judge to end the marriage instead of trying to fix it through admonishments. As al-Māturīdī also points out, it is the conditions of preserving love and mercy which is why the hitting is not allowed to be with violence. If there is already no love, then one can presumably go beyond God's limit and intent and end up hitting her with violence. So the disciplining is in al-Māturīdī's view only useful and even allowed to save a loving marriage.

<p>hand over (<i>sāqūā</i>) [the women] in dowry and expenditure.¹²⁹</p> <p>And the Exalted's statement; {and leave them in the bed}</p> <p>It has possibly two aspects:</p> <p>One: That he abandons her while a sexual state without speaking to her, [and] not that he avoids having intercourse with her; because intercourse is a right between them [and so fulfills the right] on him and leaves out [her fulfillment which is a right] on her, [and] do not injure her (<i>yu'dhīhā</i>)¹³⁰ by what damages (<i>yaḍarr</i>) his right and himself, and God knows best.</p> <p>And it is possible His statement means to abandon them in bed and in having intercourse and such of her rights; But it is her right which is upon him [to fulfill] on the condition of agreement (<i>ḥāl al-Muwāfaqa</i>)¹³¹ and preserve the limits of God (<i>ḥudūd Allāh</i>)¹³² between them, [and] not on the condition of neglect [of one's right] (<i>ḥāl al-Tadyīc</i>)¹³³, and God knows best.</p> <p>And Ibn ʿAbbās - may God be pleased with him – said: Abandon her only in having intercourse with her, and do not have intercourse with her on the bed, and and refrain from her (<i>yuwalīhā</i>) in the afternoon (<i>al-Zuhr</i>)¹³⁴, however they both participate in the disciplining; Because he disciplines himself [by refraining] from his [sexual] needs (<i>ḥājatahu</i>) which is the meaning of not having intercourse with her at that moment informing him about her desires and her needs, and gives insight into his own desires without her, and God knows best.¹³⁵</p>	<p>وقوله - تعالى - : (واهجروهن في المضاجع) يحتمل وجهين: أحدهما: أن يهجرها في حال مضاجعته إياها في ألا يكلمها، لا أن يترك مضاجعتها؛ إذ المضاجعة حق بينهما عليه في تركها ما عليها، لا يؤذيها بما يضر حقه ونفسه، والله أعلم. ويحتمل قوله: أي اهجروهن عن المضاجع ومضاجعة أخرى في حقها؛ فيكون حقه عليه في حال الموافقة وحفظ حدود الله بينهما، لا في حال التضييع، والله أعلم.</p> <p>وعن ابن عباس - رضي الله عنه - أنه قال: يهجرها في ألا يجامعها، ولا يضاجعها على فراشه، ويوليها الظهر، لكنه على هذا يشتركان في التأديب؛ لأنه به يؤدب نفسه في ذلك إلى حاجته، لكن المعنى من ذلك ألا يجامعها لوقت علمه بشهوتها وحاجتها، وإنما ينظر شهوته دونها، والله أعلم.</p>
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¹²⁹ The exact same statement is made above at p. 15. It is repeated here to present an opinion which links the sexual rights gained by both husband and wife in the spending of dowry and expenditure.

¹³⁰ The verb *yu'dhīhā* is a form IV 3rd person singular masculine subjunctive active verb from *adhā*, meaning to harm, injure or offend someone.

¹³¹ *Muwāfaqa* is a form III verbal noun of *wafaqa*, referring to be in accordance.

¹³² The limits of God (*ḥudūd Allāh*) refer to matters allowed by God in terms of sexual relations, and these are preserved by fulfilling them lawfully (i.e. marriage) so one doesn't breach the limit (i.e. adultery) which makes one accountable for judicial punishments (which are called *ḥudūd* because they are revelatory punishments (*ʿuqubāt*) for breaching them). See: Al-Zuhayli, *Al-Fiqh Al-Islamiyyu*, 5:711-815, 6:19-562.

¹³³ *Tadyīc* is a form II verbal of *ḍayaʿ*, meaning to lose, omit, waste or neglect something.

¹³⁴ See fn. 85 and 86 above.

¹³⁵ The idea that refraining from intercourse also disciplines him is a clear favorable reference to the Islamic concept of asceticism (*zuhd*). On *Zuhd*, see: *Encyclopaedia of Islam, Second Edition* (2012), s.v "Zuhd" by Geneviève Gobillot, edited by P. Bearman e.a., accessed augustus 15, 2016, http://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/encyclopaedia-of-islam-2/zuhd-SIM_8201.

<p>And The Mighty and Majestic's statement: {you shall seek no other way (<i>sabīlān</i>) against them}</p> <p>That they obeyed you, meaning: do not seek their defects (<i>ʿilālān</i>) [in their behaviour].¹³⁶</p> <p>And it was said (<i>qīl</i>): They are not charged with [the duty] to love, but God made the admonishment and abandonment and the harm in the beds [which are related to expressions of love].</p> <p>And Ibn ʿAbbās - may God be pleased with him – said: So [when] she obeys him, and no other way is for him [to discipline] her.</p> <p>Then the hitting is what we mentioned [earlier] that he hits her without violence, as was narrated from the Prophet (<i>ṣaws</i>) who said: “Cling to your whip – or breaking (<i>ḍaʿ</i>) [to train it]¹³⁷ until you think it is destroyed, and do not hit her with it [i.e. the whip]”¹³⁸, it is said (<i>qīl</i>): With what do we hit? He said: Hit with your sandal without violence, he means¹³⁹: without traces [i.e. bruises] and without disgracing her.</p>	<p>وقوله - عز وجل -: (فلا تبغوا عليهم سبيلا) إن أطعنكم، أي: لا تطلبوا عليهم عللا. وقيل: لا تكلفوهن الحب، وإنما جعل الله الموعدة والهجران والضرر في المضاجع.</p> <p>وعن ابن عباس - رضي الله عنه - أنه قال: فإن أطاعته فلا سبيل له عليها.</p> <p>ثم الضرب هو ما ذكرنا أنه يضربها ضربا غير مبرح، وهو ما روي عن النبي - صلى الله عليه وسلم - قال: " علق سوطك - أو ضع حيث يراه أهلك، ولا تضربها به "، قيل: وبم نضرب؟ قال: بنعليك ضربا غير مبرح، يعني: غير مؤثر ولا شائن.</p>
<p>And in another reported it is narrated: The Messenger of God (<i>ṣaws</i>) said: “Fear God in [your treatment] of women, so that you reproach her them with faith in God, and regard their private parts (<i>furūjahunna</i>) as lawful (<i>istahlalatum</i>) by the word of God, and that is [a right] for you [you have] over them, in order that they do not trample your bed wit someone else you hate. So publically (<i>ʿalin</i>) hit them [but] hit them without violence, and for them is upon you [the duty] of their livelihood and clothing them in common accordance.”¹⁴⁰</p> <p>And the Mighty and Majestic said: {God alone is High, [and] Great.} This - and God knows</p>	<p>ويروى في خبر آخر: قال رسول الله - صلى الله عليه وسلم -: " اتقوا الله في النساء؛ فإنكم أخذتموهن بأمانة الله، واستحللتم فروجهن بكلمة الله، وإن لكم عليهن ألا يوطئن فراشكم أحدا تكرهونه؛ فإن فعلن فاضربوهن ضربا غير مبرح، ولهن عليكم رزقهن وكسوتهن بالمعروف".</p> <p>وقوله - عز وجل -: (إن الله كان عليا كبيرا) هذا - والله أعلم - تذكير من الله عباده، وأمر منه إياهم: أنه مع علوه وسلطانه</p>

¹³⁶ The plural noun *ʿilal* refers to defects or deficiencies in something.

¹³⁷ The verbal noun *ḍaʿ* from *ḍaʿḍaʿ* and refers to breaking or training a camel, and is explained in the classical dictionary *Lisān al-ʿArab* as *yataʿddaba*, disciplining. Ibn Manẓūr al-Anṣārī, *Lisān al-ʿArab* (Beirut: Dār Ṣādr, 1993), 8:224.

¹³⁸ This Ḥadīth is unknown as a complete text, only smaller versions are known which state: “Cling to your whip until it looks destroyed”. Al-Ṭabarānī, *Ibid*, 10:285, Ḥadīth 10672. Shams al-Dīn al-Sakhāwī, *al-Maqāṣid al-Ḥusna fī bayān kathīr min al-Aḥādīth al-Mushtaharra ʿalā al-ilsinna* (Beirut: Dār al-Kitāb al-ʿArabī, 1985), 1:458-459, Ḥadīth 700. It is therefore again possible that al-Māturīdī relates an unknown version of this tradition, or paraphrases it and mixing it with his own explanation, as can be seen by inserted the “...-or breaking..”.

¹³⁹ It is unclear who he is, but we can assume it is the Prophet. I haven't been able to trace the tradition to him or any person of the early generations.

¹⁴⁰ Muslim b. al-Ḥajāj al-Naysābūrī, *Ṣaḥīḥ Muslim* (Beirut: Dār iḥyāʾ al-Turāth al-ʿArabī, n.d.), 2:886 – 1218. On the that providing sustenance gives rights to men over their wives' body, see: Hina Azam, *Sexual Violation in Islamic Law: Substance, Evidence, and Procedure* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 84–88, 120–169. And fn. 30 above.

<p>best – is a reminder (<i>tadhkīr</i>) from God to worship Him, and [serve] the command coming from Him to them [believers]: That He is with His loftiness (^c<i>Ulūhu</i>) and His commanding power (<i>Sulṭānahu</i>) and His grandeur (^c<i>Azīmatahu</i>), and His splendor (<i>Jalālahu</i>), and His power (<i>Qadrahu</i>)¹⁴¹, [and] He does not reproach with the first disobedience we commit to Him, and not with the first lapse we commit, [although] He has the power for reproachment and destroying those [who are disobedient], so you should not reproach them women – also – with their first disobedience against you¹⁴², and God knows best.</p> <p>And it is possible [to mean]: Cite this verse and others like this one; So to mention His loftiness and greatness; And preserve His limit (<i>ḥaddahu</i>) in what He created for you of disciplining, and mention His power over it [to remind and restrain you].</p>	<p>وعظمته وجلاله وقدرته، لا يؤاخذنا بأول عصيان نعصيه، ولا بأول عثرة نعثرها، مع قدرته على الأخذ على ذلك وإهلاكه إياهم، فأنتم لا تؤاخذون -أيضا- بأول معصية يعصين فيكم، والله أعلم.</p> <p>ويحتمل: ذكر هذه الآية وهو كذلك؛ ليذكر علوه وكبره؛ فيحفظ حده فيما جعل له من التأديب، ويذكر قدرته عليه.</p>
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Conclusion

In our analysis of al-Māwardī and al-Māturīdī we can sum up several major differences: 1) Māwardī's *tafsīr bi-IMathūr* sees the meaning of the Qur'ān to be reported by the early generations and closed off for the later generations to generate new meanings; 2) al-Māturīdī's *tafsīr bi-IRā'y* sees the Qur'ān as an open text whereby meanings are generated through interacting with the meanings which are reported by the early generations (*mathūr*) and human reason (*rā'y*) in the pursuit for human welfare (*maṣlahā*). *Tafsīr bi-IRā'y* therefore sees meaning as multi-vocal and hermeneutically only approachable but never determinable, as only God knows best. *Tafsīr bi-IMathūr* instead works with a closed set of possible meanings. The difference lies mainly in how one views the function of *tafsīr*. For al-Māwardī, the meaning of the Qur'ānic text is to be determined as closely as possible through traditions and linguistics, which then can be applied rationally and multi-vocally in jurisprudence (*Fiqh*) outside the science of *tafsīr*.¹⁴³ For al-Māturīdī

¹⁴¹ Here al-Māturīdī links and explains the two divine attributes (highness and greatness) with the ones mentioned here, but also to remind that only God truly has commanding and controlling power over everything, and relativizes male commanding power.

¹⁴² Here al-Māturīdī's emphasizes that one should mirror God's mercy and forgiveness when it comes to spousal disobedience and apply restraint.

¹⁴³ Al-Māwardī has written several well known works on Shafī'ī *Fiqh*.

on the other hand, *tafsīr* is *Fiqh*. This also has direct effect on how one presents human ontology. Al-Māwardī simply relates the classical views on gender ontology, while al-Māturīdī engages and opposes it. Although al-Māturīdī did believe in gender differences, he rejects to use verse 4:34 as a foundation for those differences as a way to defend the Ḥanafī rejection of required guardianship. Male superiority is generally due to some bodily differences, and when these bodily advantages disappear due to for example illness, he becomes similar to women in ontology. Although it is not stated outright by al-Māturīdī, but it is indirectly implied that general male superiority disappears when livelihood can be attained through means other than hard labour. The same can be seen in the presented views on disciplining. Al-Māwardī relates faithfully from the earlier generations that hitting is without violence, and leaves further commentary for the works of *Fiqh*. Al-Māturīdī on the other hand provides an unique and extensive *Fiqh* commentary to determine, limit, and provide conditions for the hitting to be without violence because it serves to save a marriage of love and mercy. Both al-Māturīdī's exegesis on gender ontology and on disciplining is rare, and can even be called unique within the *tafsīr* tradition, and sadly has been neglected by his followers among the Ḥanafī and other schools (as research shows, al-Rāzī leaned heavily on him¹⁴⁴). His application of *tawassuṭ* (nonaligned and independent interpretation) in matters of *tafsīr* and *Fiqh* deserves further research as the earliest form of orthodox *tafsīr bi-IRā'y*. This is especially so on his views on human ontology and how this constructs al-Māturīdī's theo-cosmology. Al-Māwardī's work shows a *Tafsīr bi-IMathūr* development which sifted out Prophetic traditions, and instead focused on the multiple opinions of the early generations in combination with linguistics and minimal *Fiqhi* discourse. Both methodologies present weak, strong, and preferred meanings, to not only construct and determine the meaning of the Qur'ān, but also to show the width of Islamic hermeneutics.

¹⁴⁴ See: Saleh, fn. 11. Arnold Yasin Mol, "Laylat al-Qadr as Sacred Time: Sacred Cosmology in Sunni Kalām and Tafsīr", in *Islamic Studies Today: Articles in Honor of Andrew Rippin*, edited by Walid Saleh and Majid Danesghar (Leiden: Brill, 2016).

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